

Design and Construction of Virtual Welding Training System for the Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW)

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بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

وَلَوْ أَنَّ فِي الْأَرْضِ مِنْ شَجَرَةٍ أَقْلَامٌ وَالْبَحْرُ يَمُدُّهُ مِنْ بَعْدِهِ

سَبْعَةُ أَبْحُرٍ مَا نَفِدَتْ كَلِمَاتُ اللَّهِ إِنَّ اللَّهَ عَزِيزٌ حَكِيمٌ

(لقمان) (27)

**In the name of Allah, the Compassionate, the
Merciful**

**And if all trees in the earth were pens and the seas,
were ink of it with seven more seas added after it, the
words of Allah would not be exhausted. Undoubtedly,
Allah is Honorable Wise.**

Luqman. 27

To My Family

Parents and Wife

To My Brothers, Sisters and Friends

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Certification

I certify that the PhD thesis “**Design and Construction of Virtual Welding Training System for the Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW)**” which is being submitted by **Raheem Khazal Musawel** was prepared under my supervision at the University of Basrah, College of Engineering as a partial fulfillments requirement for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Mechanical Engineering.

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ABSTRACT

In practical welding processes, special requirements are needed. Welding metals, electrodes, welding machine and fume suction machine...etc are needed to train welders. The present work suggests building a soft or virtual training laboratory that can simulate most of the conditions of practical welding processes.

In last two decades, several patents registered around the world in the virtual welding machine and during the last three years the first and the second international virtual welding conferences occurred in Germany.

The current study allows the operator to simulate and experience most of the conditions found in welding. It teaches the hand-eye coordination skills necessary in welding, provides immediate feedback so the trainee knows if the arc length effect, welding angles, or the correct travel speed, welding electrode burn-off, and records all mistakes, which lead in general to minimize the training cost and reducing the training period.

In the current project, a training of welders for Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) can be performed close to reality. To keep the information about the experiments on virtual welding simulator and the users who performed the experiments, a database management and reporting system has been built. With this software the results can be shown as graphics and scoring.

Low cost sensors are used in design and construct the current Virtual Welding System. Ultrasound, infrared, optical rotary encoder, linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) and inertial measurement unit (IMU) sensors are used. The constructed virtual welding system consists from a major virtual view system (Helmet and 22" LCD touch screen) and virtual tools system (Welding Gun & coupons) in addition to PC and several types of converters. The converters consist of analog to digital converter (ADC) and Video Graphics Array (VGA) converters in addition to several electrical conductors to change the power supply sources depending upon the software control.

The Helmet is developed to be more compatible with virtual welding and real welding, so that the main shape of the helmet is stilled same as real prototype while the polarized screen replaced with 8" DVD screen and AV camera. When the virtual welding process occur the Helmet DVD screen will receive data from PC (Virtual

Welding Process) while when the process stop the Helmet DVD screen will receive data from AV Camera to represent the real environment.

Six virtual welding case studies are studied; these case studies covered most welding positions in the Shielded Metal Arc Welding. Flat plate, flat groove and Tee sections are studied for horizontal, vertical and overhead positions. Effects of the arc length, travel speed and welding angles are studied. The given results are good accepted and the trainees became more able to deal with real welding.

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Nomenclature

1. Symbols	
Symbol	Description
c	Cosine
$o_1x_1y_1z_1$	Rotated frame
$o_0x_0y_0z_0$	Original frame
q	Quaternion
r_{ij}	Rotation matrix at element i,j
R_1^0	Transformation matrix (from coordinate 1 to coordinate 0)
R_x^θ	Transformation Matrix of rotate about x-axis
R_y^θ	Transformation Matrix of rotate about y-axis
R_z^θ	Transformation Matrix of rotate about z-axis
s	Sine
x_0	Original position in X-direction
x_1	Rotated position in X-direction
y_0	Original position in Y-direction
y_1	Rotated position in Y-direction
z_0	Original position in Z-direction
z_1	Rotated position in Z-direction
Greek	
ϕ	Roll Angle
θ	Pitch Angle
ψ	Yaw Angle
2. Abbreviations	
Symbol	Description
1F	Flat position fillet weld
1G	Flat position groove weld
2D	Two Dimensions
2F	Horizontal position fillet weld
2G	Horizontal position groove weld
3D	Three Dimensions
3F	Vertical position fillet weld
3G	Vertical position groove weld
4F	Overhead position fillet weld
4G	Overhead position groove weld
A	Alpha
AC	Alternating Current

ADC	Analog to Digital Converter
APIs	Application Programming interfaces
ARC+	Virtual welding training commercial brand
AV	Audio Video
BasVW	Basrah Virtual Welding System
CS WAVE	Virtual welding training commercial brand
CTWD	Contact Tip to Work Distance
DC	Direct Current
DCM	Direction Cosine Matrix
DVD	Digital Versatile/Video Disc
E	Electrode
EKF	Extended Kalman Filter
EWI	Edison Welding Institute
FCAW	Flux Cored Arc Welding
GDI	Graphics Device Interface
GMAW	Gas Metal Arc Welding
GND	Ground
GSI SLV	Virtual welding training commercial brand
GTAW	Gas Tungsten Arc Welding
IAB 089	International Welders Standard
IAB 252	International Welding Engineers Standard
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
LED	Light-Emitting Diode
LVDT	Linear Variable Differential Transformer
MIG	Metal Inert Gas
NC	Not Connected
PC	Personal Computer
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
RS232 DE9	Recommend Standard PC serial port of 9 pins
SAW	Submerged Arc Welding
SDK	Software Development Kits
SMAW	Shielded metal Arc Welding
TIG	Tungsten Inert Gas
USB	Universal Serial Bus
V-D	Vertical Down
VGA	Video Graphics Array
VN-100	Vectornav -100
VR	Virtual Reality
VRSim	Virtual welding training commercial brand

VRTEX360™	Virtual welding training commercial brand
VS2010	Visual Studio 2010 Software
VSS	Voltage Supply
VW	Virtual Welding
VWTS	Virtual Welding Training Systems
WPS	Welding Procedure Specification

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Chapter One

Introduction

Chapter One

Introduction

1.1 Introduction to Virtual Welding

Welding is a practical skill that requires continual practice and careful attention to the variables that the welder controls to improve [1]. Welding is a complex industrial process which often requires several trials before it can be done right. Welding is the key technology for fabrication and assembly of metal structures. In some industries, most notably automotive, welding is done primarily by robots or automated machinery. In many industries such as shipbuilding, heavy equipment production, and small parts fabrication, welding is a value added operation that is largely a manual process applied by humans. Training of new welders is a significant activity both for industry and for the vocational education community. Training is especially important for welders working on critical items such as pressure vessels, nuclear piping, and naval ships, where welds have high quality requirements and are carefully inspected. It is estimated that the combined annual welder training costs for all U.S. shipyards is in excess of \$5M [2].

The deducing of training cost is a major goal of all industrial establishments, one of the costs deducing methods is using reality environment to simulate welding processes.

The manual SMAW process still accounts for a significant share of the total welding filler-metal business. This is largely due to the many advantages of the SMAW process, including exceptional versatility, low equipment costs, convenient power source requirements, low maintenance costs, durability, a relatively straightforward operation, and a simple set-up [3].

In this chapter, a background review on major arc welding methods will be introduced; a view on the shielded metal arc welding method (SMAW) and the virtual environment methods will be studied.

1.2 Arc Welding Types

There are many types of arc welding, they are classified according to welding arc to the below types:

1. Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW)
2. Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW)
3. Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW)
4. Flux Cored Arc Welding (FCAW)
5. Submerged Arc Welding (SAW)

1.2.1 Shielded metal arc welding (SMAW)

The SMAW process is an arc welding process which produces coalescence of metal by heating them with an arc between a covered metal electrode and the work. Shielding is obtained from decomposition of the electrode covering. Pressure is not used. Filler metal is obtained from the electrode [4].

Figure 1.1 indicates the SMAW process where many parameters affected on the welding process such as direction of welding, arc shape, weld pool, solidification weld metal, molten weld metal and electrode construction that will be studied in the present work.

Figure 1.1 Shielded metal arc welding (SMAW) process diagram [5]

1.2.2 Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW)

Gas Tungsten Arc Welding is an arc welding process which produces coalescence of metals by heating them with an arc between a tungsten (non-consumable) electrode and the work. Shielding is obtained from a gas or gas mixture. Pressure may or may not be used and filler metal may or may not be used [4].

In some welding references and texts this process has sometimes been called Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) welding. Figure 1.2 indicates the GTAW process.

Figure 1.2 Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW) process diagram [3]

1.2.3 Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW)

Gas Metal Arc Welding can be considered as an arc welding process which produces coalescence of metals by heating them with an arc between a continuous filler metal (consumable) electrode and the work. Shielding is obtained entirely from an externally supplied gas or gas mixture [4]. Several methods of this process are called MIG (Metal Inert Gas) or CO₂ welding (non-preferred terms). Figure 1.3 indicates GMAW process.

Figure 1.3 Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW) process diagram [3]

1.2.4 Flux Cored Arc Welding (FCAW)

Flux cored arc welding (FCAW) is a fusion welding process in which weld heating is produced from an arc between the work and a continuously fed filler metal electrode. Atmospheric shielding is provided completely or in part by the flux sealed within the tubular electrode, Figure 3.1. Extra shielding may or may not be supplied through a nozzle in the same way as in GMAW [6].

Although the process was introduced in the early 1950s, it represented less than 5% of the total amount of welding done in 1965. In 2005, it passed the 50% mark and is still rising. The rapid rise in the use of FCAW has been due to a number of factors. Improvements in the fluxes, smaller electrode diameters, increased reliability of the equipment, better electrode feed systems, and improved guns have all led to the increased usage [6].

Figure 1.4 Flux Cored Arc Welding (FCAW) process diagram [6]

1.2.5 Submerged Arc Welding (SAW)

It is an arc welding process which produces coalescence of metals by heating them with an arc or arcs between a bare metal electrode or electrodes and the work. The arc is shielded by a blanket of granular, fusible material on the work [4]. Pressure is not used and filler metal is obtained from the electrode and sometimes from a supplementary welding rod. The SAW process diagram indicates in Figure 1.5

Figure 1.5 Submerged Arc Welding (SAW) process diagram [3]

1.3 Shielded Metal Arc Welding

Shield metal arc welding (SMAW) is the most common type of an arc welding process that melts and joins metals, but its research is less than other types of welding such as gas tungsten arc welding (GTAW) and inert gas metal arc welding (GMAW) [4].

This thesis describes a virtual environment to simulate SMAW control system which has replaced real training with virtual one. The advantages and disadvantages of shielded metal arc welding (SMAW) can be given by:

1.3.1 Advantages of SMAW

SMAW have many advantages, the main advantages of SMAW can be written as [3]:

1. High -quality welds are made rapidly at a low cost.
2. This SMAW process can be used in all positions such as flat, vertical, horizontal, or overhead, and also can be used for welding most structural and alloy steels.
3. It requires only inexpensive, portable, and the simplest equipment as compared to other arc welding processes.
4. Used on great variety of materials and used with many electrode types & sizes, that is giving the user high flexibility to use wide range of electrode types and sizes.
5. It is especially useful for work in remote areas where portable fuel powered generators can be used as the power supply.
6. Because SMAW has simplicity, adaptability, versatility and can weld many metals in all positions from near minimum to maximum thickness; it is one of the most widely used arc welding processes.
7. The electrode provides both the shielding and the filler metal. Auxiliary gas shielding or granular flux is not required.
8. The process is less sensitive to wind and draft than some other arc welding processes.

1.3.2 Disadvantages of SMAW

The main disadvantages of SMAW can be given as [3]:

1. Electrode becomes shorter and periodically needs replacing i.e. the limited length of the electrode (about 35cm) means the welding process is frequently interrupted and the working time is badly utilized, and requires electrode changing once the electrode is consumed.
2. The many stops typically mean that the arc is only ignited 25-60% of the working time.
3. Comparing with the cost of the time and materials needed to deposit the weld metal, SMAW is clearly inferior to GMAW. SMAW deposits the weld more slowly than does GMAW. This process requires that slag be cleaned at starts and stops and before depositing a weld bead next to or onto a previously deposited bead.
4. Current limited by resistance heating of electrode. Temperature must not exceed "Break Down" temperature of covering.
5. Unless removed completely, the solidified slag can cause severe corrosion of the weld area and lead to failure of the weld.
6. The gas shield in SMAW is not clean enough for reactive metals.
7. Limitation placed on current that can be used (High amperages cannot be used)

1.3.3 Typical SMAW Setup

The typical setup of the AC or DC machine of Shielded Metal Arc Welding Machine can be given below:

1. Welding power source (suitable for work to be performed)
2. Length of suitable welding cable
3. Length of suitable ground cable
4. Suitable electrode holder
5. Suitable ground clamp
6. Covered electrode (matched to base metal)
7. Welding helmet and protective equipment

The main parts of the SMAW machines can be shown in Figure 1.6.

Figure 1.6 Elements of a SMAW circuit diagram [1]

A constant current type power source is most commonly used, these are available in AC, AC/DC combination or DC output with mechanical, electrical, solid state controls, either static or dynamic.

Constant current power sources come in a large variety of output characteristics, capacities and controls. They can be static or dynamic. All AC and AC/DC combination static power sources require single phase input (primary power) [3].

The industrial classes are usually re-connectable on different voltages i.e. 230, 460 or 575; while the limited input machines are single voltage connection i.e. 208, 230 or 575 [3].

Most of the DC output machines require three phase primary power. These are also normally re-connectable on different voltages. There are well over 150 different types of covered electrodes in use today; within the mild, low alloy-stainless and specialty steels alone.

1.3.4 SMAW Electrodes Classification

In welding electrode classifications, there are two famous systems; U.S. System and Canadian (CND) system. The classification covered mild steel electrodes and low alloy steel electrodes. Table 1.1 shows a conversation between U.S. System and Canadian (CDN) System [4].

Table 1.1 SMAW US vs. Canadian (CDN) conversation systems

U.S. System	Canadian (CDN) System
Example : <u>E6010</u>	Becomes : <u>E41010</u>
Where:	Where
E = Electrode	E = Electrode
60 = Min tensile strength in 1000 psi	410 = Min tensile strength in (MPa)
1 = Usability position	1 = Usability position
0 = Type of covering, current, polarity	0 = Type of covering, current, polarity
0 = All positions with excellent vertical down (V-D) features 1 = All positions except vertical down (V-D) 2 = Flat, horizontal 3 = Flat only 4 = Vertical down	

1.4 Welding Positions

There is essentially four different fundamental welding positions, namely flat, horizontal- vertical, overhead and vertical position. Vertical position welding can be carried out as vertical upward or vertical downward welding. In addition, fillet welds can be made in the horizontal-vertical position or in the flat position. The symbol F given for Fillet welds while the symbol G given for Groove welds. The famous names for welding position are 1F(Flat position fillet weld), 2F (Horizontal position fillet weld), 3F(Vertical position fillet weld) , 4F(Overhead position fillet weld), 1G(Flat position grove weld), 2G(Horizontal position groove weld), 3G(Vertical position groove weld) and 4G(Overhead position groove weld), see Figure 1.7 [1] .

Figure 1.7 Welding positions

1.5 Virtual Reality Environments

In virtual environments, the rendering quality of 3D models and scenes directly affects the user evaluation. Virtual reality techniques have been widely used in many areas such as entertainment and aeronautics. They have changed the life of people in many aspects. Reality and real time are the two key attributes of Virtual reality techniques. Without them we have no feeling of being as in a real world when we browse in a virtual environment [7]. Texture mapping is one of the most widely used techniques for realistic rendering in virtual reality systems. Virtual Reality can add realism and improve analysis method in ergonomic design.

Virtual reality (VR) based skill training simulators are highly interactive computer systems that allow for training of e.g. manipulation skills [7]. In the most complex domains, such as in surgery, teaching correct manipulation requires expert's judgment and instructions.

Virtual reality (VR) based system has an advantage to provide an experience which never be realized in the real world. In these years, medical training simulators are developed by VR-based system. The aim

of medical VR training system is to teach the actual manipulation in surgery. At the same time, the most important feature is that the system can teach anatomical and physiological behaviors. Interactive learning by VR system is expected to motivate active learning effectively [8].

1.6 Virtual Welding

VR simulations with mixed reality haptic displays are routinely used for training surgeons in laparoscopic techniques. Commercial pilots train almost exclusively on flight simulator platforms [9]. It is expected that a VR environment could be used to improve the effectiveness of welding training activities.

A prototype mixed reality system was created to allow a human to make a virtual shielded metal arc welding (SMAW) in different welding positions. The system records process parameters, which are displayed after welding for critique and instruction. This represents a first of its kind welder training approach that leverages current state-of-the art VR technology which is capable of integration into the product simulation [9].

1.7 DirectX Application

DirectX is the Microsoft collection of Application Programming interfaces (APIs) that are designed to give game developers a low-level interface to the PC hardware that is running Windows. DirectX refers to a collection of objects you can incorporate in a program to build a game[10]. Currently on version 11.0, each DirectX API component provides access to different aspects of the hardware, including graphics, sound, and networking, all through a standard interface. This interface allows developers to write their games using one set of functions, regardless of the hardware they're being run on [11].

In the present work, Microsoft Windows®7 and DirectX11 Software Development Kit (SDK) are used to get real time pictures for the virtual welding process by using simple webcam and VS2010 software. The developed program enables to get picture of 640*480 resolution within each 10ms.

1.8 Graphics Device Interface (GDI)

The Graphics Device Interface (GDI) is a Microsoft Windows application programming interface and core operating system component responsible for representing graphical objects and transmitting them to output devices such as monitors and printers.

GDI is responsible for tasks such as drawing lines and curves, rendering fonts and handling palettes. It is not directly responsible for drawing windows, menus, etc.

GDI's most significant advantages over more direct methods of accessing the hardware are perhaps its scaling capabilities and its abstract representation of target devices. Using GDI, it is very easy to draw on multiple devices, such as a screen and a printer, and expect proper reproduction in each case. Simple games that do not require fast graphics rendering use GDI. The Graphics Device Interface (GDI) provides Windows applications with a device-independent interface to the screen and printers. The GDI is a layer between the application and the different types of hardware. This architecture frees the programmer from having to deal with each type of device directly by letting the GDI resolve differences in hardware instead [12].

In the present work GDI and Visual Studio 2010 are used to get image processing for the pictures which get from the webcam to indicate the real time position of the tip of the welding electrode. More discussions will be studied in next chapter.

1.9 Thesis Objectives

The main objectives of this concept are to:

1. Design and construct a virtual welding machine to teach new welding trainees and help the trainers which lead to minimize the training cost, training time and welding health problems.
2. Reduce the whole cost of constructed system by using low cost sensors.

3. Solve the required equations and build and software in VB.net to make the programs ready to use from the welding trainees and trainers.
4. Study the trainees' performance according to the trainees' feedback to the change of major welding parameters; welding travel angle, welding working angle, welding travel speed and welding arc length.
5. Study the effect of using image analysis with linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) sensor and touch screen tools to find the simulate arc welding length and compare new technique cost with high cost laser sensors.
6. Study the ability of using inertial measurement unit (IMU) which consists of accelerometers, gyroscopes and magnetometers to find the rotation matrix components which lead to find Euler angles in aeronautical space Yaw, Roll and Pitch and the ability to use these angles to find welding working angle and travel angle.

Chapter Two
Literature Review

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

Training of new welders is a significant activity both for the vocational education community and industry field. As soon as the training is important in all fields, this important concerned in special fields such the welders who are working on critical items such as pressure vessels, nuclear piping, and naval ships, where welds have high quality requirements and are carefully inspected. They are several ways to train new welders, the main major lines of training can be given in three fields, computer assist in welding training, real time monitoring in welding processes and virtual reality in welding training. In this chapter, a historical review for all these fields will be mentioned.

2.1 Computer Assist in the Welding Training

On the second line, computer assist in the welding training, where a real welding used with assist of sensors and computer software programs to learn the new welders and to develop the skills of trainers. Several literature and patents around the world are published.

Harvey and Macy (1975) [13] registered a patent in USA on "Arc Welding Simulator Trainer". An arc-welding simulator was provided for teaching welder trainees how to arc weld quality welds resulting in significant savings of time and material. Specifically, the simulator provides immediate, discriminative feedback and the capacity for concentrated practice, both learning qualities lacking in the welding process.

Bruce (1978) [14] registered a patent in USA on "Device for teaching and evaluating a person's skill as a welder", An apparatus for simulating an arc welding operation, for training welders and for evaluating a welder's performance including a target representing a simulated weld to be made, mechanism for imparting predetermined motion to the target, a simulated welding tool including a simulated welding rod and a holder for the rod, the rod having a free end with an element adjacent thereto having properties capable of being sensed magnetically, a magnetic sensor assembly located adjacent to the target for movement therewith and including members capable of responding to

the presence of the magnetic field produced by the magnetic element on the rod for producing responses depending upon the position of the simulated welding rod, the magnetic sensor assembly including angularly related pairs of opposed sensor members arranged to produce responses to represent the position of the simulated welding rod relative thereto in two different angularly related directions.

Boris et al (1987) [15] registered a patent in USA when they built a "welder's trainer". The welder's trainer comprises an welding electrode simulator, an electric-arc welding heat balance electronic model, a welding situation visual synthesis electronic model, a welding situation simulator made in the form of a television-type display, to which the welding situation visual synthesis electronic model is connected, and a training control and monitoring unit connected to the display through the visual synthesis electronic model.

Boris et al (1987) [16] registered a second patent in USA when they built an "Electric Arc Trainer for Welders". An arc trainer for welders comprises a welding electrode simulator, a welding object simulating unit, a welding power source whose outputs are connected to the electrode simulator and to the welding object simulation unit. The unit controls the quality of the simulated welding process of feedback signals for the trainee, which is connected to the welding electrode simulator and to the welding power source. The unit monitors variations of welding parameters, which is connected to the control unit and to the welding power source. The control unit also connects to a helmet.

Donald et al (1990) [17] registered a patent in USA on "Device for Training Welders". A device for training, evaluating and providing practice for welders and particularly welders and welder students that use MIG, TIG and welding devices that employ movable consumable welding rods. The device includes a video monitor having a cathode ray tube, the face of which has visual displays thereon, including displays from which simulated welding parameters can be entered and displays which simulate different welding joints with a welding target to be followed by the operator while holding the selected welding tool. The device uses a microprocessor and related electronic devices programmed to generate the displays and to control the various machine operations. The device also includes a unique way to produce the various control

responses necessary to the operation including optical and electromagnetic responses.

Geert (2009) [18] registered a patent in European Patent Office when built "A device for assisting in manual welding using a plurality of mark light projecting units". The application relates to a device for assisting in manual welding for indicating one or more welding locations onto a workpiece and mounting arrangement.

Boulware and Forquer (2012) [19] presented a real welding training machine using motion capture cameras to get the welding parameters such as work angle, travel angle, Contact Tip to Work Distance (CTWD), travel speed and proximity. The model built in Edison Welding Institute (EWI). The screen of prototype model compares a trainee's technique for new trainees versus all their prior trials for this Welding Procedure Specification (WPS). In this system a real arc used and it is valid for Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW), the welding position which covered by this system are 1G (stringer and single pass), 1F (fillet and lap single pass) and 2G (stringer single pass), while the system do not cover 2F, 3G... etc.

2.2 Real Time Welding Monitoring System

There are many leading experts' literatures around the world on using real time monitoring system in welding processes. In real time monitoring system many several types of sensor are used to study the welding processes. Sensors feedback information may be used to study many welding parameters such as temperature distribution in welding process, welding geometry, electrode consumption, etc... This type of literatures is used to study and develop the welding process and do not use to give skills to the trainers. Several of these literatures briefed here, first without using external sensors while the rest using optical, ultrasound, infrared and laser sensors.

Cook et al. (2008) [20] gave a historical perspective of arc sensing which including the use of arc sensing in: (a) automatic voltage control with gas tungsten arc welding for arc length control, (b) consumable electrode processes for arc length control, and (c) seam tracking and fill control as demanded by automatic pipe welding, robotic welding, and other critical automated welding applications. Some of these, such as

automatic voltage control, date back over 40 years. The advantage of arc sensing is that by using the arc it as a sensor there is no need for external sensors with their associated costs and concern for reliability in the harsh welding arc environment.

Saeed (2008) [21] gave a brief overview to introduce the optical sensor technologies and the techniques used to sense the weld pool state in different applications. In the welding community, various optical sensors and sensing systems, especially charge-coupled devices, have been applied widely to realize real-time monitor of welding processes. One or more characteristic parameters of the welding process measured by optical sensors are sent to an established control model to realize process control for various welding applications. The light source sensed by the optical sensor can be either the strong arc light radiation in the welding process or the external illumination light for imaging purposes.

Yang and Wikle (2008) [22] discussed the use of infrared sensors for real-time welding process monitoring and weld quality control. In order to better understand the measurement principles of infrared sensors, a general description and the physics of infrared sensors are presented first. Next, the use of thermal distributions to monitor weld characteristics are explained, along with a comparison of the thermocouple and thermography techniques for thermal distribution measurement. Variations in the weld process parameters, such as current, voltage, and welding speed, distinctly alter the thermal distributions. Therefore, the weld characteristics, which are controlled by the process parameters and material characteristics, can be tracked by monitoring changes in the thermal distributions.

Shao and Yan (2008) [23] reviewed the ultrasonic sensing techniques developed for real-time monitoring of welding processes. It begins with a brief description of the ultrasonic sensing principle including general information of ultrasound and ultrasonic sensors before moving on to the ultrasonic techniques, i.e. acoustic emission testing and ultrasound testing, and their applications to real-time monitoring of welding processes. Ultrasonic sensors are used to convert electrical pulses/other forms of energy into mechanical vibrations or vice versa. For the applications to the real-time monitoring of welding processes, ultrasonic sensors have been used in two distinct ways, i.e. acoustic

emission testing and ultrasonic testing. The advantages and limitations of each technique are also discussed in addition to a summary on ultrasonic sensors for welding process monitoring.

Ancona and Sibillano (2008) [24] studied the information about the degree of penetration during laser welding can be obtained by looking down the laser with detectors mounted near the focusing optics or, when complete penetration is achieved, under the workpiece. Laser welding is a highly automated process that is being used more and more in the automotive industry. The advantages of laser welding include high speed, deep penetration, high aspect ratio of the joints, and low thermal distortion. To further improve the efficiency of the laser welding systems, quality assurance measures are increasingly required directly into the production processes. Traditional off-line inspection of welds is expensive, reduces productivity, and requires dedicated test equipment and people

2.3 Virtual Reality in Welding Training

In general, Virtual Reality (VR) is currently being used as a training tool in a number of different application areas including medicine, aviation, and military [25].

In the welding training, virtual reality environments are used without using any real welding processes occur; couples of sensors and software construct to represent welding processes. In this field there are several patents and technical papers are published, most of these literatures may be consider as a secured documents where did not including useful information for researchers such as types of sensors and motion equations.

In the last decade the term of "Virtual Welding (VW)" became widely used instead of "Virtual Reality in Welding Training". The new term "Virtual Welding" enter the search field, the literatures in virtual welding (VW) can be subdivided into two groups, virtual welding models developments, and virtual welding applications.

2.3.1 Virtual Welding Models Developments

Michel and Dominique (2003) [26] registered a patent in France. The new patents depending one simulate welding process for teaching by apprenticeship of a manual task such as arc welding. In this project a moveable system guide the motion of the welding electrode on the workpiece while there is computer software used to make a necessary analysis to get the required welding parameters.

Aiteanu et al (2003) [27] developed a new welding helmet for the manual welding process. The welders working conditions are improved by augmenting the visual information before and during welding. The image is improved providing a better view of the working area. An online quality assistant is available during welding, suggesting the correction of the guns position or pointing out welding errors, by analyzing the electrical welding parameters. Assembly advisors suggest the assembly sequence, by displaying the type and the position of the following piece into the actual ensemble. In addition, an available online documentation of the welding process gives an opportunity to reduce the effort of post process quality assurance which often uses expensive x-ray investigations.

Wilhelm (2004) [28] studied the remote control of real and virtual welding robots for learning. In this study; an application of a Mixed Reality concept to Internet-Based Robotics was presented and argued how a coupling of real and virtual, local and remote robot systems may support a cost oriented training and education in context related robotics. This application is related to describe complex effort/flow driven automation systems distributed over real and virtual worlds. It allows selected materialization of parts of the system in reality and is functionally connected to a simulation model.

Mavrikios et al (2006) [29] built a prototype virtual reality-based demonstrator for immersive and interactive simulation of welding processes. This paper investigated the use of virtual reality (VR)-based methods to support human integrated simulation for manual welding processes. Within this concept, a prototype demonstrator has been developed, called 'the virtual welding environment', which provides functionality for an immersive and interactive process execution within a

virtual environment. The simulation features of this environment enable the user to set up, execute and validate the results of a welding process. This environment demonstrates a promising potential for supporting process design and training procedures related to manual welding.

Park et al (2007) [30] studied the design and evaluation of an augmented reality welding helmet. Development and ergonomic evaluation of an augmented reality welding helmet was described. The system provides an augmented user interface with supporting information relevant to the welding process. The experimental studies focused on hand–eye coordination of welders and non-welders with two prototypes of the augmented reality welding helmet. The first prototype operated at 16 frames per second, whereas the second, improved version had 20 frames per second. In addition, the hand–eye coordination while wearing the welding helmet with video see-through head-mounted display was compared to a performance with natural vision, without any helmet. Experimental results showed significant influence of helmet and occupation on hand–eye coordination. Subjective assessment revealed better rating for stereo perception for the system with the higher frame rate, whereas no significant difference in performance was found between the two frame rates.

Dongsik et al (2009) [31] studied the Visualization of Virtual Weld Beads. In this paper, a visualization method of weld beads for a welding training under virtual environments was presented. To represent virtual beads, a bead shape is defined according to the datasets which consist of bead width, height, angle, penetration acquired from real welding operations. A curve equation of bead's sectional shape is mathematical modeled, and a height map is generated according to this numerical equation, which is used for generating the bead's mesh data using its height information. Finally, virtual weld beads are visualized in real-time according to the accurately simulated results from user's input motion.

Teeravarunyou and Poopatb (2009) [32] developed a computer-based welding training system. This system used in welding shops, and it has been developed to facilitate and to substantially enhance the basic skills in Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW). The process is begun by creating a tool that captures the skill performance from the intermediates

group into coded knowledge. Afterwards a software tool shows how to transfer knowledge by using the principles of learning feedback. Sixty novices were assigned to use the training system with the T weld welding position. The results showed that novices could significantly increase their welding skills after using the feedback in arc length, work angle and travel angle, while the performance of welding speed is unimproved; all the three inspectors rated the quality of welding in feedback group higher than non-feedback group.

Zboray et al (2010) [33] registered a patent in USA on "Virtual Reality Pipe Welding Simulator". A simulator facilitates virtual welding activity of pipe and open root weld joints. The simulator may include a logic processor based system operable to execute coded instructions for generating an interactive welding environment that emulates welding activity on a section of virtual pipe having at least one virtual weld joint. It also includes a display connected to the logic processor based system for visually depicting the interactive welding environment, wherein the display depicts the section of virtual pipe. A mock welding tool is provided for performing virtual welding activity on the at least one weld joint in real time where one or more sensors are adapted to track movement of the input device in real time for communicating data about the movement of the input device to the logic processor based system.

Peters et al (2011) [34] registered a patent in USA on "Welding Simulator Console". The simulator console can be represented as a trolley machine similar to the real welding machine provided with 15 " LCD screen. As occur in the most published patents, the technical information was hidden except some details described patent figures such as views of the welding simulator console (front, left, top, etc...).

2.4 Virtual Welding Applications

In industrial field, welding simulation development started in earnest during the past decade in three countries: the U.S., Canada, and France. Teams in each country tackled the challenge differently, and each emerged with its own technologies, but all have the same overarching goal: to make weld training more effective [35].

Claude Choquet (2008) [36] president of 123Certification Inc. in Montreal, is a welding engineer who has focused his research on the

simulation of manual and semiautomatic processes. The company's ARC+® simulator, first implemented fully in 2006, depicts a virtual environment through 3D glasses inside a welding helmet. Seven years in development, the system tracks the gun motion through special markers, similar to those used for surgery simulations. It involves motion tracking, metallurgical processing (of the bead characteristics), and 3D image rendering.

Across the Atlantic, a French vocational training organization had the idea of virtual welding training, and in 2001 it contracted with CS, a French conglomerate. By 2003 the company had developed its first prototype. Dubbed CS WAVE, the technology differs from ARC+ in that it doesn't use a welding helmet and the welding action happens on a screen that can be moved into the horizontal or flat position. The welding gun uses gyroscopic and ultrasonic technology to detect position. The student simulates welding motion by moving the gun across the simulated, on-screen weld joint. During the past year, in fact, CS has been negotiating to team up with 123Certification to market simulators under one common product line. [35].

In the U.S., the impetus for a virtual welding system came from the Navy Joining Center, managed under the auspices of the Edison Welding Institute (EWI) in Columbus, Ohio. The government, through the Navy Manufacturing Technology (ManTech) Program, provided funds to develop a virtual welding system, originally for training employees at General Dynamics Electric Boat Corp. The project set the stage for initial development. EWI teamed up with VRSim, an East Hartford, Conn.-based firm that until that time had focused its efforts on virtual reality training for prototyping and maintainability studies. The software code had to balance material properties with the heat from the arc, as well as the overall weld parameters—not a simple task, and it took three computer processors to sift through all the data. The project's first phase focused primarily on whether a machine could accurately simulate welding graphically in a virtual environment. After success, by about 2005, with ManTech money running out, VRSim took the reins to see if it could develop a marketable product. The project showed some real promise, but the system would have retailed for about \$300,000 [35].

In 2010 the view of virtual welding system became more active and the believers of the ability of these systems to solve the welding training problems increase rapidly which led to first meeting on virtual welding study, the 1st Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER 2010 "The Future of Education" in Germany. In this conference eleven technical papers with five products are shown.

Ahrens and Keitel (2010) [37] studied the virtual training in GSI company depending on computer based training and communication Platform. A new method for practical training and new aspects in material testing found according to the virtual training , the study built upon more than thousand trainee and extended for about four years, the conclusions of this study are : theoretical education in welding and inspection will strongly be influenced by computer based training and e-learning platforms, practical training of welders will be split into virtual welding, training with simulators, and real classical welding training and finally welding education will be combined with additional education like nondestructive testing and corrosion protection.

Bornert (2010) [38] indicated the elements of the realistic education of welders to educate welders near to the practice. The decisive differences of the concept compared with other solutions are presented and their advantages are discussed. A several technical changes are constructed and many specifications of the customers studied. The first approaches of the integration of virtual tools for the training of welders were presented.

Benus and Dalto (2010) [39] considered the virtual welding training is a key to minimize the very expensive training cost. Several technologies studies to speed the virtual welding up, to cut the training cost and enhance the training quality to give the trainer more flexibility. The potential benefits, the feedbacks of the users (trainers and trainees) are studied, the various uses depending on the various training curriculum and the final acceptance or rejection of the systems are studied and presented.

Kreindl (2010) [40] indicated that the virtual welding reduces consumption of the values of steel, aluminum or copper plate, shielding gas, welding current and filler metal by up to 25% by comparing of real

training course of 2 sessions with 60 hours of practical training. The final result is the virtual training costs are lowered and the environment and the climate are protected.

In the last few years some highly developed systems of welding trainers have come to the market that in the meantime have reached a high technical state of development.

Rautert (2010) [41] from The Bildungszentren Rhein-Ruhr establishment in Germany studied five virtual welding systems and compared to each other within the scope of tests by different groups (apprentices, orienting measures for young people and welders' training). The results shows that each system have several advantages than others which lead to say all the five tested systems are accepted and the ability to select depending upon the preferences of the customer.

Hillers et al (2010) [42] used a new technologies evolve to the welding educational to support the beginner for getting started in the subject of welding. In this study, the Virtual reality (VR) system is studied with an approach of using the paradigm of Augmented Reality. The trainees saw the physical welding piece with a virtual welding view. The labels are registered by a camera which is mounted in a welding helmet, so that the pose of both is tracked in real time. The camera fulfills besides the tracking as well the video documentation of the exercise. As an option the system may be used during real welding to broaden the integration into the educational process from pure virtual welding to document real welding.

Richard et al (2011) [43] studied the Physical and Cognitive Effects of Virtual Reality Integrated Training .The objective of this study was to evaluate the cognitive and physical impact of virtual reality (VR) integrated training versus traditional training methods in the domain of weld training. The background of this study depend on the fact of the weld training is very important in various industries and represents a complex skill set appropriate for advanced training intervention. As such, there has been a long search for the most successful and most cost-effective method for training new welders. Method: Participants in this study were randomly assigned to one of two separate training courses taught by sanctioned American Welding Society certified welding

instructors; the duration of each course was 2 weeks. After completing the training for a specific weld type, participants were given the opportunity to test for the corresponding certification. Participants were evaluated in terms of their cognitive and physical parameters, total training time exposure, and welding certification awards earned. Each of the four weld types taught in this study represented distinct levels of difficulty and required the development of specialized knowledge and skills.

Yunus (2011) [44] identified the suitability of VR welding simulator application towards Computer Based Training in assisting new trainees to developing welding skills at the Centre of Instructor and Advanced Skills Training Shah Alam Selangor and National Youth Skills Institute Pagoh Johor. The significance of the study is to create a computer-based skills development approach in welding technology as well as to cultivate the elements of general skills among them. This study is also important in elevating the number of individual knowledge workers (K-workers) working in manufacturing industry in order to achieve a national vision, which is to be an industrial nation by the year of 2020. The design of the study is a survey type of research which uses questionnaires as the instruments, and some 136 were interviewed. The analysis for the questionnaires will be conducted by the using Statistical Package for Social Science 15. Descriptive analysis is used to identify the frequency and mean. The findings of the study show the welding technology skills have developed in the trainees as a result of the application of VR simulator at a high level (min=3.89) and the respondents agreed that the skills could be embedded through the application of the VR simulator (78.01%). In summary, this VR simulator is suitable in welding skills development training in terms of exposing new trainees to the relevant characteristics of welding skills and at the same time spurring the trainees' interest towards learning more about the skills.

Dongsik et al (2012) [45] studied the real-time graphical presentation from empirical data for virtual welding tasks. A method of real-time graphical presentation from empirical data for welding tasks under virtual reality (VR) environments: visualized virtual situations with datasets produced from real operations, considered the welding shape and

real datasets for visualization and carried out a comparison study: more than 90% accuracy

Bednarzik et al (2012) [46] concluded that the machine hour rate of GSI SLV Schweißtrainer is about 20% less than that of the welding booth. This result depends on the utilised capacity of the workshop, the health risk can be reduced to 50% , the practical relevance of the GSI SLV Welding Trainer will be assessed at 45% ,as a result, a scoring system is developed to make a competition students. Finally after several traing coursese they found with new tools of training the recommended training time should not be longer than 1 week.

New comercial trade mark " ARC+" developed by Gray and Richter as a virtual welding syetem [47]. A new form of welding process visualization where the hand movement and complete welding process can be followed on the integrated touch screen and (when connected) large screen TV/projector. ARC+ have vairy options such as it is the only supplier worldwide that has perfected the infra-red camera tracking technology, no magnetic field pollution, motion stightness , travel and work angle, nozzle plate distance and welding speed, root penteration, and weld size are availble to get in this system.

Peters and Wallace (2012) [48] in Iowa State University studied the effect of using virtual welding system from Lincoln Electric Company, 1G, 2F, 3F, 3G positions are tested by using two groups of trainee 50% VR and 100% VR . The aim of test to get the effect of correct position, Contact Tip to Work Distance (CTWD), work angle, travel angle and travel speed. Very good results get for both 1G and 2F that the certificate rate reaches 80% for 50% VR trainee group while it is increase to 100% for 100% VR trainee group. On other positions (3F and 3G) the results decreased rapidly for both group of trainee so that they concluded that virtual welding system is very good tool for beginner trainees.

Eng (2012) [49] utilize the virtual welding technology and activity based training in order to transfer skills in a Life-Long Learning context. Through the years the European Welding Federation and International Institute of Welding have managed to develop an international harmonized guideline for education of welding personnel.

These guidelines have ensured a harmonized technological content and have created the foundation for international acceptance of certificates and diplomas that ensure the free movement of welding personnel worldwide. Through the introduction of virtual welding technologies these costs have been reduced and skills upgrade facilities have been enhanced.

Havenith et al (2012) [50] prepared a first term to construct a complete study course for Virtual Welding Training System. The Principles of a complete education course depend upon planning, performing and verifying welding process. The education model is developed by increasing degree of difficulty from easy to difficult, taking of welder's exams of one level. The training total course time extended for 6 days.

Middeldorf (2012) [51] indicated the guidelines for the use of Virtual Welding Training Systems (VWTS), this study can be considering one of the best attempts to construct VWTS course. In this study all steps are continuously linked and flexibly mixed to continuously move between the virtual and the real world, furthermore this study is depend on the universal standards such as International Welders (IAB 089) and International Welding Engineers (IAB 252).

Rein and Biallas (2012) [52] studied welding ergonomics in novice and expert welders using virtual welding, the research questions are: what are the differences between novice and expert welders with regard to posture? And which health related problems can be identified based on these differences? In this study many comparisons occurs between 6 experts and 7 novices by using Lincoln Electric© VRTEX360™ machine. Both groups had no prior experience with virtual welding. For weld quality the performance index located between 50% and 60% for both professionals and beginners. For Neck musculature for both right and left side the results of beginners is higher than professionals. For Lower back musculature the results of the right side is higher than left side for beginners groups while the differences between left and right sides are very limited in professionals group. In general this study may be summarize to clear postural differences between expert and novice welders, less asymmetric muscular activation in experts, more upright posture in experts and more frontal posture in experts.

2.5 General Summary of Literatures Review

In general among the three welding education fields (real time monitoring in welding processes, computer assist in welding training and virtual reality in welding training), the last filed of virtual welding studies increases as rapidly. During the last decade about several patents are registered around the world and new markets for such training are opened. The current project tries to design and construct of a virtual welding machine in Shielded Metal Arc Welding by using low cost sensors and instruments. The study depends upon design a welding gun and as welding electrode and modified the real helmet with LCD screen and camera. The performance of the constructed system will be test in welding training centers to vitrify the general welding parameters; welding working angle, welding travel angle, welding travel speed and welding arc length.

Chapter Three

Theoretical Background

CHAPTER THREE

Theoretical Background

3.1 Rigid Motions and Homogeneous Transformations

A large part of inertia moment units (IMU) kinematics is concerned with the establishment of various coordinate systems to represent the positions and orientations of rigid objects and with transformations among these coordinate systems. Indeed, nowadays, IMU has become cheaper and more accessible as there are many hand-phones which are equipped with this sensor and camera as well. In this chapter, the operations of rotation and translation and an introduction of the notion of homogeneous transformations will be studied to get the required welding angles. Homogeneous transformations combine the operations of rotation and translation into a single matrix multiplication will be used to get the required direction cosine matrix that will lead to get the welding angles.

3.2 Rotations in Three Dimensions

In three dimensions, each axis of the frame $o_1x_1y_1z_1$ is projected onto the coordinate frame $o_0x_0y_0z_0$ as indicated in figure 3.1. The resulting 3×3 rotation matrix is given by [53],

$$R_1^0 = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \cdot x_0 & y_1 \cdot x_0 & z_1 \cdot x_0 \\ x_1 \cdot y_0 & y_1 \cdot y_0 & z_1 \cdot y_0 \\ x_1 \cdot z_0 & y_1 \cdot z_0 & z_1 \cdot z_0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.1)$$

Where R_1^0 is a matrix whose column vectors are the coordinates of axes of frame $o_1x_1y_1z_1$ expressed relative to the frame $o_0x_0y_0z_0$.

Figure 3.1 Rotation About z_0 [53]

If the frame $o_1x_1y_1z_1$ is supposed to rotate through an angle θ about the z_0 -axis and by convention the positive sense for the angle θ is given by the right hand rule; that is, a positive rotation of θ degrees about the z -axis would advance a right-hand threaded screw along the positive z -axis as indicated in figure 3.1, so that:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 \cdot x_0 &= \cos\theta & y_1 \cdot x_0 &= -\sin\theta \\ x_1 \cdot y_0 &= \sin\theta & y_1 \cdot y_0 &= \cos\theta \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

$$z_0 \cdot z_1 = 1$$

All other dot products are zero, thus the resulting transformation matrix R_1^0 is given by:

$$R_1^0 = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\theta & -\sin\theta & 0 \\ \sin\theta & \cos\theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.3)$$

The transformation (3.3) is called a basic rotation matrix, and since the rotation occurs about the z -axis, so the transformation (3.3) can be written as:

$$R_z^\theta = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\theta & -\sin\theta & 0 \\ \sin\theta & \cos\theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.4)$$

Similarly, the basic rotation matrices can be extended to represent the rotations about the x and y -axes are given as:

$$R_x^\theta = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos\theta & -\sin\theta \\ 0 & \sin\theta & \cos\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.5)$$

$$R_y^\theta = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\theta & 0 & \sin\theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin\theta & 0 & \cos\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.6)$$

3.3 Euler Angles

A common method of specifying a rotation matrix in terms of three independent quantities is to use the so-called Euler Angles. Consider the fixed coordinate frame $o_0x_0y_0z_0$ and the rotated frame $o_1x_1y_1z_1$ shown in figure 3.2

Figure 3.2 Euler angles representation [53]

The orientation of the frame $o_1x_1y_1z_1$ relative to the frame $o_0x_0y_0z_0$ can be specified by three angles (φ, θ, ψ) , known as Euler Angles, and can be obtained by three successive rotations as follows: First rotate about the z -axis by the angle φ . Next rotate about the current y -axis by the angle θ . Finally rotate about the current z -axis by the angle ψ . In figure 3.2, frame $o_a x_a y_a z_a$ represents the new coordinate frame after the rotation by φ , frame $o_b x_b y_b z_b$ represents the new coordinate frame after the rotation by θ , and frame $o_1 x_1 y_1 z_1$ represents the final frame, after the rotation by ψ . Frames $o_a x_a y_a z_a$ and $o_b x_b y_b z_b$ are shown in the figure only to visualize the rotations. In terms of the basic rotation matrices, the resulting rotational transformation R_1^0 can be generated as the product by using equations (3.4), (3.5) and (3.6) which are denoted by s and c for

representing the sine and cosine respectively, the resulting rotation matrix R_1^0 of frame $o_1x_1y_1z_1$ expressed relative to frame $o_0x_0y_0z_0$ is given by [53]:

$$R_1^0 = R_{z,\phi}R_{y,\theta}R_{z,\psi} \quad (3.7)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} c_\phi & -s_\phi & 0 \\ s_\phi & c_\phi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c_\theta & 0 & s_\theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_\theta & 0 & c_\theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c_\psi & -s_\psi & 0 \\ s_\psi & c_\psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} c_\phi c_\theta c_\psi - s_\phi s_\psi & -c_\phi c_\theta s_\psi - s_\phi s_\psi & c_\phi s_\theta \\ s_\phi c_\theta c_\psi + c_\phi s_\psi & -s_\phi c_\theta s_\psi + c_\phi s_\psi & s_\phi s_\theta \\ -s_\theta c_\psi & s_\theta s_\psi & c_\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.8)$$

3.4 Roll, Pitch and Yaw Angles

A rotation matrix R also can be described as a product of successive rotations about the principal coordinate axes X , Y , and Z [53]. These rotations are defined the roll, pitch, and yaw angles, ϕ , θ , and ψ will be referred to roll, pitch, and yaw angles respectively as indicated in figure 3.3

Figure 3.3 Roll, pitch and yaw angles

Yaw, Roll and Pitch are aeronautical terms for rotation using the Euler angles, relative to the local coordinate system of an aircraft [53]. In order to navigate an aircraft, its orientation about the aircraft's center of mass must be known. This orientation is known as the aircraft attitude and is comprised of three rotations:

- Roll (ϕ) – A 360° rotation about the aircraft body x-axis.
- Pitch (θ) – A 180° rotation about the aircraft body y-axis.
- Yaw (ψ) – A 360° rotation about the aircraft body z-axis

The rotation matrix for the (ψ , ϕ , θ) sequence is obtained by concatenate the transformation matrices as shown below [48].

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_1^0 &= \begin{bmatrix} c_\phi & -s_\phi & 0 \\ s_\phi & c_\phi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c_\theta & 0 & s_\theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_\theta & 0 & c_\theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_\psi & -s_\psi \\ 0 & s_\psi & c_\psi \end{bmatrix} \\
 &= \begin{bmatrix} c_\phi c_\theta & -s_\phi c_\psi + c_\phi s_\theta s_\psi & s_\phi c_\psi + c_\phi s_\theta c_\psi \\ s_\phi c_\theta & c_\phi c_\psi + s_\phi s_\theta s_\psi & -c_\phi s_\psi + s_\phi s_\theta c_\psi \\ -s_\theta & c_\theta s_\psi & c_\theta c_\psi \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.9)
 \end{aligned}$$

The rotation matrix (3.9) can be extended to a general rotation matrix R where the R elements values is depending upon the values of ϕ , θ , and ψ and upon the directions of the rotation, therefor the general rotation matrix can be written as [53]:

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & r_{13} \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & r_{23} \\ r_{31} & r_{32} & r_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.10)$$

The matrix in equation (3.10) is named as the Direction Cosine Matrix (DCM) where its elements are necessary to determine the angles ϕ , θ , and ψ [49]. The entire matrix element in equation (3.10) is the same of the matrix in the equation (3.9).

In order to find the required angles in matrix (3.9), it is useful to begin with θ by using $r_{31} = -s_\theta$. This equation can be inverted to yield

$$\theta = -\sin^{-1}(r_{31}) \quad (3.11)$$

However, one must be careful in interpreting with this equation. Since $\sin(\pi - \theta) = \sin \theta$, there are actually two distinct values (for $r_{31} = \pm 1$) of θ that satisfy Eq.(3.11). Therefore, both the values are valid solutions.

$$\theta_1 = -\sin^{-1}(r_{31}) \quad (3.12)$$

$$\theta_2 = \pi - \theta_1 = \pi + \sin^{-1}(r_{31}) \quad (3.13)$$

For finding the values of the corresponding angles ψ , it is easy to note: $r_{32}/r_{33} = \tan \psi$ or:

$$\psi = \tan^{-1} \frac{r_{32}}{r_{33}} \quad (3.14)$$

Since $r_{32} = c_\theta s_\psi$ and $r_{33} = c_\theta c_\psi$, so the value of ψ depends on the value of θ which means there are two values also for ψ . If eq.(3.14) is modified as below :

$$\psi = \tan^{-1} \frac{\frac{r_{32}}{c_\theta}}{\frac{r_{33}}{c_\theta}} \quad (3.15)$$

The eq. (3.15) is valid for all cases except when $c_\theta = 0$, for each value of θ there are two values of ψ , and eq. (3.15) can be written as:

$$\psi_1 = \tan^{-1} \frac{\frac{r_{32}}{c_{\theta_1}}}{\frac{r_{33}}{c_{\theta_1}}} \quad (3.16)$$

$$\psi_2 = \tan^{-1} \frac{\frac{r_{32}}{c_{\theta_2}}}{\frac{r_{33}}{c_{\theta_2}}} \quad (3.17)$$

In order to find the value of third angle φ , a similar way can be used where $r_{21} = s_\varphi c_\theta$ and $r_{11} = c_\varphi c_\theta$:

$$\varphi = \tan^{-1} \frac{\frac{r_{21}}{c_\theta}}{\frac{r_{11}}{c_\theta}} \quad (3.18)$$

Again, eq. (3.18) is valid for all cases except when $c_\theta = 0$, for each value of θ there are two values of φ , and eq. (3.18) can be written as:

$$\varphi_1 = \tan^{-1} \frac{\frac{r_{21}}{c\theta_1}}{\frac{r_{11}}{c\theta_1}} \quad (3.19)$$

$$\varphi_2 = \tan^{-1} \frac{\frac{r_{21}}{c\theta_2}}{\frac{r_{11}}{c\theta_2}} \quad (3.20)$$

For a special case when $\theta = \pi/2$ and $-\pi/2$, the angle θ will be linked. This phenomenon is called Gimbal lock. Although in this case, there are an infinite number of solutions to the problem [54]

3.5 Gimbal Lock

Gimbal lock is the name given to a problem that occurs with the use of Euler angles [54]. Because the final rotation matrix depends on the order of multiplication, it is sometimes the case that the rotation in one axis will be mapped onto another rotation axis. Even worse, it may become impossible to rotate an object in a desired axis. Gimbal lock is the loss of one degree of freedom in a three-dimensional space that occurs when the axes of two of the three gimbals are driven into a parallel configuration, "locking" the system into rotation in a degenerate two-dimensional space as shown in figure 3.4[55]. All three gimbals can still rotate freely about their respective axes of suspension. Nevertheless, because of the parallel orientation of two of the gimbal axes there is no axis available to accommodate rotation along one axis.

Figure 3.4 Gimbal lock in rotation [55]

3.6 Quaternions

In computer graphics applications, quaternions are used to represent three-dimensional rotations [55]. Quaternions extend the concept of rotation in three dimensions to rotation in four dimensions. This avoids the problem of "gimbal-lock" and allows for the implementation of smooth and continuous rotation.

A Quaternion is defined using four floating-point values $[x \ y \ z \ w]$. These are calculated from the combination of the three coordinates of the rotation axis and the rotation angle. In order to understand what a quaternion is and why it is useful first, one needs to be aware of the alternative means of attitude representation. Hopefully it is familiar with the Euler angle representations of attitude, of which one is the 3-2-1 rotation sequence most commonly known as yaw (or heading), pitch, and roll. These three angles work well for most applications. Since the Euler angles are a three-dimensional vector that represents a three-dimensional attitude it is easy to just look at the numbers and get a feel for what they intuitively mean.

As indicated in the last section "gimbal lock", there is one problem with the Euler angle attitude representation; there exists two attitudes such as when pitch angle is equal to 90 degrees. In this case, the yaw and roll perform the same operation. One way to get around this problem is to add an additional degree. This is what the quaternion does in a very simplistic sense. The quaternion is based upon the principal of Euler's principal rotation. A rigid body or coordinate reference frame can be brought from an arbitrary initial orientation to an arbitrary final orientation by a single rigid body rotation through a principal angle ϕ about the principal axis; the principal axis is a judicious axis fixed in both initial and final orientation.

3.7 Quaternion Used by VectorNav

While different organizations use different ordering of the terms, all quaternions fundamentally represent the same thing. Here are the equations for each of the terms used in this quaternion (see appendix B).

$$\begin{aligned}
q_0 &= e_x \sin\left(\frac{\vartheta}{2}\right) \\
q_1 &= e_y \sin\left(\frac{\vartheta}{2}\right) \\
q_2 &= e_z \sin\left(\frac{\vartheta}{2}\right) \\
q_3 &= \cos\left(\frac{\vartheta}{2}\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{3.21}$$

Where $e = \begin{Bmatrix} e_x \\ e_y \\ e_z \end{Bmatrix}$ represents the principal axis and ϑ is the principal angle.

The fourth term q_3 is known as the scalar term. The attitude (Yaw = 0, Pitch = 0, Roll = 0) is represented in quaternion form as $q = [0, 0, 0, 1]$. The values of Euler angles -depending on the sequence rotation of (yaw, pitch, and roll) - can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
yaw &= \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{2(q_0q_1 + q_3q_2)}{q_3^2 - q_2^2 - q_1^2 + q_0^2}\right) \\
pitch &= \sin^{-1}(-2(q_0q_2 - q_1q_3)) \\
roll &= \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{2(q_1q_2 + q_0q_3)}{q_3^2 + q_2^2 - q_1^2 - q_0^2}\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{3.22}$$

3.8 The Kalman Filter

A Kalman filter is simply an optimal recursive data processing algorithm [56]. It is an algorithm that uses a series of measurements observed over time, produce estimates of unknown variables. There are many ways of defining optimal, dependent upon the criteria chosen to evaluate performance; one aspect of this optimality is that the Kalman filter incorporates all information that can be provided to it. It processes all available measurements. For example, to determine the velocity of an aircraft, one could use a Doppler radar or the velocity indications of an inertial navigation system, or the pilot and static pressure and relative wind information in the air data system. Rather than ignore any of these outputs, a Kalman filter could be built to combine all of this data and

knowledge of the various systems' dynamics to generate an overall best estimate of velocity [57].

In general Kalman filtering is a set of mathematical equations that provide an efficient way of calculating the past, present and future state of a process in a way that minimizes the amount of error introduced by the measuring process [56]. The filter is a very powerful tool and has been widely used in vision and tracking systems. In present work the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) which is considered as the nonlinear version of the Kalman filter is used to get the rotation angles form Vectornav VN-100.

Chapter Four

Experimental Model

CHAPTER FOUR

Experimental Work

4.1 Introduction

The construction of virtual welding system consist from major virtual view system (Helmet and 22" LCD touch screen) and virtual tools system (welding gun & coupons) beside to PC and several types of converters. The converters consist of analog to digital converter (ADC) and Video Graphics Array (VGA) converters in addition to several electrical conductors to change the power supply sources. Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.2 show the block diagram and the whole system of the present virtual welding training system.

Figure 4.1 Virtual Welding System Block Diagram

Figure 4.2 Virtual Welding Training Machine (BasVW1.1)

The main parts of the electronic circuit which be indicated in Figure 4.3 are consisting of:

1. LabJack , Analog to Digital Converter [see appendix C].
2. External power supply.
3. VGA convertor.
4. Welding electrode motor driver.
5. Hard Disk.
6. Helmet RS232 DE9 Pin outs.
7. Welding Gun Simulator RS232 DE9 Pin outs.
8. External Fan.
9. PC power supply.
10. PC mother board.

Figure 4.3 Main electrical circuit

The constructed model can be used as a mobile unit without needing for external computer since it is including main parts of the computer. The main electronic circuit can be shown in appendix F. The system provided with external fan for heat dissipating and two external coms for connecting the virtual welding gun and Helmet as shown in figure 4.4. The system also was provided with four USB ports in front side of the system to get and add data to the system.

Figure 4.4 External RS232 DE9 Pin outs for the system connection

4.2 Virtual View System

Developed welding helmet and touch screen are used to representative virtual welding process; the helmet design is modified to become more compatible with the virtual welding process. The major change in modified helmet is represented by removing polarized screen pad and replacing it with an 8" DVD screen. When the welding gun becomes near to the coupons sample or near to the 22" LCD touch screen– as will be explained in the next section- the helmet 8" DVD screen will be received data from the PC via video to VGA convertor. The main shape of the video to VGA convertor is indicated figure 4.5

Figure 4.5 Video to VGA converter

The video to VGA convertor makes it possible to connect the VGA card to fixed frequency monitors and video projectors. For some applications and system combinations, some additional software is needed to get the system working.

The second modification in the helmet occurs by adding low cost AV camera in the front side of the helmet, the AV camera connects directly to the 8" DVD screen. The purpose of these types of cameras is to make a real system overall view without taking off the helmet. In the helmet, modification the 8" DVD screen will be received two types of data, the first represents the virtual welding process, which receives from PC, and the other represents real overall view of the system, which receives from the AV camera. The exchange between the 8" DVD screen for the two types of picture sources (PC and AV camera) occur automatically depending upon programming the value of the signal of the arc length sensor as will be indicated in the next sections. Figure 4.6-A

and Figure 4.6-A indicated the external and internal view of modified welding helmet

Figure 4.6-A External View of Modified Welding Helmet

Figure 4.6-B Internal View of Modified Welding Helmet

4.3 Welding Gun Simulator

The construction welding gun simulator consists of several sensors and 12V DC motor. The main purpose of the welding gun simulator is to produce a simulated environment of the real welding process especially in Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW). A steel screw shaft with small gear box connects with 12V DC motor are used to represent the consumption of the real welding electrode as indicated in figure 4.7

In this section, the arc length sensor, electrode consumption sensor, travel speed sensors and welding angles sensors will be studied.

Figure 4.7 Welding Gun Simulator

4.4 Incremental Encoders

An encoder is an electromechanical device that can measure the motion or the position [58]. Most encoders use optical sensors to provide electrical signals in the form of pulse trains, which can be translated into motion, direction, or position. One of the simplest applications of rotary encoders is the mechanical computer mouse. A mechanical mouse has two rotary encoders: One for X position and one for Y position. As the

mouse moves, each encoder outputs square wave pulses. The number of pulses indicates how far the mouse has moved in the X or Y direction.

The term encoder is used for a device that provides a digital output because of angular or linear displacement. An increment encoder detects changes in angular or linear displacement from some datum position, while an absolute encoder gives the actual angular or linear position. Figure 4.8 shows the basic form of an incremental encoder for the measurement of angular displacement. A beam of light, from perhaps a light-emitting diode (LED), passes through slots in a disc and is detected by a light sensor, e.g. a photodiode or phototransistor. When the disc rotates, the light beam is alternately transmitted and stopped and so a pulsed output is produced from the light sensor. The number of pulses is proportional to the angle through which the disc has rotated, the resolution being proportional to the number of slots on a disc. With 60 slots then, since one revolution is a rotation of 360° , a movement from one slot to the next is a rotation of 6° . By using offset slots, it is possible to have over a thousand slots for one revolution and so much higher resolution [59].

Figure 4.8 Basic form of an incremental encoder

4.5 LVDT Displacement Sensor

The Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT) is an electromechanical device that produces an electrical output proportional to the displacement of a separate nonmagnetic movable core [58]. The LVDT is a high-tech instrument used to measure the elongation, vibration, thickness, expansion and so on. It is intended for wide applications in Aerospace, Machinery, Construction, Textile, Railway, Coal mine, Metallurgy, Plastic, Chemical industry and Academic research. DC LVDT performs excellently from 9-28 voltage DC power supply, suitable for high precision and high repeatability measurements with output standard signal of 0-5v or 4-20mA [58]. Figure 4.9 shows the linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) which is used as displacement sensor.

Figure 4.9 LVDT displacement sensor [58]

The LVDT sensor can be classified depending upon the output of the sensor to three types, voltage output model , two wires current output wiring , and Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) wiring (two wires current output) . The diagram for voltage output model, which is used in the present work, is shown in Figure 4.10

Figure 4.10 Diagram for LVDT voltage output model

4.6 Arc Length Sensor

The Arc Length is the term used to describe the distance from the tip of the electrode to the base metal and can be varied from lightly touching the metal at an angle sufficient to maintain an arc to a distance far enough from the base metal to extinguish the arc [4].

If the electrode is held in contact with the work using a slight angle to maintain the arc it is referred to as the drag technique. This technique is often used to weld in the flat and horizontal positions, especially with larger or iron powder electrodes. If contact with the base metal is made too quickly however; the electrode will stick or freeze to the metal. Another method to employ is to allow a slight gap between the electrode tip and the base metal. The length of the arc gap affects the appearance of the weld.

The welding machines used in Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) are known as Constant Current machines which mean that the current stays relatively constant through changes in the voltage. The machine increases the voltage as the arc length is increased to maintain a current flow at the amperage level set on the machine. If the voltage is increased too much the arc may become unstable and result in a poor quality weld. The correct arc length may vary according to the type of electrode and the position of welding [59].

One of the major difficulties in virtual welding systems is how to represent arc welding to get the actual distance between the tips of electrode and welding coupons.

Several methods are used around the world to represent arc length; the results of these methods depend upon the type of sensors. Ultrasound, infrared (IR) and laser sensors are used for this purpose, in IR and ultrasound sensors the cost of the system considered as accepted or cheap but the results are not quite good since in most types of the IR and ultrasound the accuracy range is ± 2 cm while in the laser sensor the results are quite good but the cost is very expensive as compare with the IR and ultrasound types.

In the last years a new technique is used to represent the whole system, this technique depends on the type of sensors called as pilot sensors. A new system may be considered as a similar to solar system where there is a major receiver similar to the Sun and several pilot sensors similar to the Plants , this type gives a very good results but its cost is still very expensive and more than laser sensors.

In the present work a new cheap technique is used with very accepted results. In this technique a linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) used to represent the arc length with an accuracy range of ± 2 mm. The external transmitter mechanical size of outer diameter is $\Phi 8$ mm is used with external transmitter. The output cable can be provided with free conductor ends or a connector; the Barrel type LVDT can output standard signal of 0-5 V or 4-20 mA [see appendix D].

A linear calibration is applied to make the measured value compatible with real values of welding arc length. Low cost, light weight and high response to the load change may be considered as advantages of this type of LVDT.

When the user pushes the welding gun simulator in direction of the welding coupons or indirection of the 22" touch screen, the (LVDT) voltage value change between minimum and maximum values and this change will be sent as online data to the ADC.

Controlling the arc length is very important by making sure that the electrode is not too close to the base metal. If the electrode is too close or the arc length is too short, the weld will be bad. [60]

The correct arc length varies with each electrode and application. As a good starting point, arc length should not exceed the diameter of the metal portion (core) of the electrode, e.g. a 3.2 mm (1/8-in.) 6010 electrode is held about 3.2 mm (1/8 in.) off the base material. The optimal arc length, or distance between electrode and puddle, is the same as the diameter of the electrode (the actual metal part within the flux covering) [60]. Figure 4.11 shows the recommended arc length in both common welding begin methods; scratching and tapping [60].

Figure 4.11 The recommended arc length in tapping and scratching methods [60].

In the virtual welding training system it is very important to represent the behavior of arc length change. The arc length change is depending upon the feedback of the input voltage value of LVDT to the ADC as illustrated below:

- When the value of the arc length sensor (LVDT) is lower than with minimal recommended arc length value, the system will be indicated (stick), while when the LVDT value is greater than the recommended arc length value, the system will stop the virtual welding process.
- When the value of LVDT is between the maximum and minimum recommended arc length values, the helmet 8" DVD screen will receive data from PC (virtual welding process). In this case, the

software provides two parallel lines indicate the variation of arc length as shown in Figure 4.12. The distance between the two parallel lines varied according to the value of arc length sensor (LVDT), when the value of arc length sensor (LVDT) within the recommended values, the color of the two parallel lines will be green, otherwise the two parallel lines color will be red which mean in general the trainee must be stopped the process since the maximum recommended value, the software will change helmet 8" DVD screen source from PC (welding process) to source of AV camera.

Figure 4.12 Two colored parallel lines indicate the recommended arc length

4.7 Electrode Consumption Sensor

The burn off rate or the linear rate of consumption of a consumable electrode is considered as one of the main parameters in the welding process [1].

A 12V DC motor, small gearbox and a rotary optical encoder are used to control a screwed shaft to make a simulation for the welding electrode consumption. A rotating optical encoder is connected to the motor shaft to make a feedback for a corrected length of the electrode shaft between any two welding processes; the data is transferred from the optical encoder to the ADC. The position of the electrode is considered as

a function of the electrode length, when the position of the electrode indicated 0 position that means the electrode length is the total length (30 cm) while when the position of the electrode indicates 30 cm that means the electrode must be replaced and between these values it is considered as the present length of welding electrode. The control process occurs in two stages:

- ❖ In the first stage the software prepares the system to start up by checking the welding position value which was saved from the last training process, when the value is not equal to zero the software will send a command to the motor to run till it reached the zero position depending upon the feedback of the rotary optical encoder.
- ❖ In second stage the first trainee will be able to use the system, in this case when the trainee pushes the welding electrode in direction of coupons or indirection of the touch screen the virtual welding process will begin and there are several actions will occur in same time:
 1. The software will check the value of the arc length sensor (LVDT), if it is accepted then
 2. The software will be sending a signal to the 12V DC motor to run to represent the electrode consumption.
 3. The software will be sending a signal to the 8" DVD screen in the Helmet to receive data from PC to represent virtual welding process.
 4. The rotary optical encoder will be sent online values to ADC indicate the instantaneous position of welding electrode.
- ❖ When the LVDT reading is unaccepted values of arc length the software will be stopped the DC motor motion and 8" DVD screen in the Helmet will be received data from AV camera.
- ❖ When the trainee correct his hand position and the LVDT reading accepted arc length values, the virtual welding process will starts again and the 8" DVD screen in the Helmet will receive data from PC when the 12V DC motor will run.

4.8 Travel Speed Sensors

The rate of travel across the joint is controlled by the welder during welding and greatly affects the appearance and strength characteristics of the weld.

The amount of weld metal deposited (weld deposition rate) and the travel speed may vary with the type and size of electrode being used. The correct weld speed will result in a well-formed weld bead that shows good fusion, penetration and a gradual transition of weld metal into the corners of the joint [59]. A weld speed that is too fast results in a thin stringy weld with poor strength. A weld bead that is too slow a speed will result in a heavy weld that has too much convexity [59].

To represent a travel speed in virtual system three types of sensors are used, an ultrasound sensor, infrared sensor, and an image processing obtained from an external webcam camera.

In the IR and ultrasound sensors the output data (analog voltage) are calibrated to represent displacement and the resulting travel speed is obtained by dividing the displacement to the virtual welding process time. IR and ultrasound sensors are insufficient when the distance between the sensors and reflecting wall are too low (in general less than 8 cm which is called the sensor dead zone), to overcome this problem, the reflecting wall must be far greater than this distance.

In the present work, both IR sensor and ultrasound sensor are constructed in the welding gun simulator where the data is received to the PC via ADC.

An indirect way is also used to get travel speed by analyzing the data which is the obtained from image processing by using external webcam with the virtual welding process time

4.9 Welding Angles Sensors

In the Shielded Metal Arc Welding (stick) process, the welder must control two electrode angles. The first angle is the one formed between the electrode and the base metal, called the work angle. The second angle is the angle that the electrode is held at relative to the direction of travel, called the travel angle.

The travel angle for the flat, horizontal and overhead can be either pulled or pushed while the travel angle for the vertical can be either upward or downward as indicated in Figure 4.13[4].

Figure 4.13 Working angle and travel angles direction

The work angle should be the one that places the weld metal between the members to be welded in the manner desired. The weld metal will be deposited in a relatively straight line from the tip of the electrode to the work. The decision to push or pull is largely one of experience and practicality.

There are several difficulties to represent both traveling and working angles since the trainee must learn the effect of changing both types of angles. Both welding angle changes are depending upon the instantaneous position of the trainer hand so that using sensors to get instantaneous angles is necessary.

In the present work an inertial measurement unit (IMU) is used to obtain online values for both angles. The Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) usually consists of accelerometers, gyroscopes and magnetometers. Traditionally, the IMU has been used to estimate the position and orientation of airplanes, missiles etc. Recently, the size and cost have decreased making it possible to be used for many applications such as augmented reality and body motion analysis.

In the present work, a software is built to get the orientation angles from the IMU depending upon the values of Direction Cosine Matrix (DCM). The value of Pitch angle used to represent working angle while the Roll angle is modified for using as a travelling angle.

4.10 Vectornav VN-100 Sensor

The VN-100 module is the smallest Attitude and Heading Reference System (AHRS) on the market and is also the first available in a surface mount package. These features make the VN-100 module ideal for incorporating accurate and reliable device orientation information in your compact embedded electronic designs. This user manual details the specifics of the VN-100 module and describes how to embed it into our electronic system.

The VN-100 uses a right-handed coordinate system. A positive yaw angle is defined as a positive right-handed rotation around the Z-axis. A positive pitch angle is defined as a positive right-handed rotation around the Y-axis. A positive roll angle is defined as a positive right-handed rotation around the X-axis. The axes direction with respect to the VN-100 module is shown in figure 4.14.

Figure 4.14 VN-100 Coordinate System

4.11 General Considerations for Using the VN-100

The VN-100 relies on magnetic and acceleration measurements in order to solve for orientation, however, when the quality of the magnetic and acceleration measurements deteriorates so will the accuracy of the solution. This can be mitigated to some level by using active tuning and especially external to the sensor body field effects can be rejected this way (external magnetic and acceleration disturbances). However, when embedding this module in an electronics assembly one invariably will expose the VN-100 to nearby hard (magnetized metallic components) and soft (e.g. nickel batteries) iron magnetic effects. If one does not compensate for this it will adversely affect the performance of the VN-100.

The VN-100 internal architecture combines a full 3-axis set of accelerometers, magnetometers, and angular rate gyros that send analog outputs through low pass filters prior to digital conversion. After the analog voltages have been digitized they run through calibration models with factory calibrated coefficients. This calibrated data is then made available as outputs from the device and also to the embedded filter. Based on the user configurable flash settings, the VN-100 then uses a Kalman filter algorithm to solve for the orientation and bias-free gyro rates.

4.12 Virtual Welding Coupons

The present work comes with the most widely used welding coupon, so a five welding coupons (Flat Plate, Tee Joint, Groove Joint, 2" diameter XXS Pipe and 6" schedule 40 pipe) that can be used in multiple positions. All the coupons are produced from plastic; Figure 4.15-4.17 indicate three types of coupons. All these coupons are manufactured and ready to use.

4.13 Electronic Circuit Design

4.13.1 Welding Gun Simulator

To connect all the parts and sensors to the welding Gun Simulator RS232 DE9 Pin outs is used, female one connected to the main system and the other connect to the welding Gun simulator. There are 8 wires connected as shown in table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Welding Gun Simulator Connections

Item	Description
1	VSS 5V DC
2	Motor turns counter
3	VSS 12V DC
4	Ultrasound Sensor
5	GND
6	Motor Motion (Forward)
7	Motor Motion (Backward)
8	NC
9	LVDT Sensor

4.13.2 Helmet Connection

In Modified Helmet connection also RS232 DE9 Pin outs is used but in this part only four pins are used, two of them are 5V DC and 12V DC where there is one pin for ground connection while the most important pin is the pin whose is connect the camera. The Helmet connection is shown in table 4.2.

Table 4.2 Helmet Connections

Item	Description
1	NC (Not Connected)
2	NC
3	NC
4	NC
5	Video in
6	VSS 12V DC
7	Camera
8	NC
9	GND

In the 8" screen in the helmet received two of data sources; the first from computer VGA screen and the second from AV camera, thus, when the virtual welding occurs the helmet screen will receives data from the computer VGA and the virtual welding process will appears in both screens 8" DVD screen in helmet and in 22" LCD Screen. When the virtual welding process stops, the helmet screen will receives data from the VGA camera. The convertor between the computer source and camera source occur via small conductor as shown in Figure 4.18 according to:

- A (0 V) and B (12V), the transistor (C1815) will be normally closed, and then the 8" DVD helmet screen will receives signal from camera (the trainee see real environment).
- A (5 V) and B (0 V), the transistor (C1815) will be normally opened, and then the 8" DVD helmet screen will receives signal from VGA computer screen (the trainee see virtual welding process).

Figure 4.18 Helmet screen control conductor

4.13.3 External Power Supply Connection

The external power supply provides the required power for the system, so it is supply 5V DC and 12V DC, the main connections of the external power supply can be shown in table 4.3.

Table 4.3 External power supply connections

Item	Description	Voltage
1	All sensors in the Welding Gun Simulator	5V DC
2	USB (External in front side of BasVW 1.1)	5V DC
3	DC Motor in Welding Gun Simulator	12V DC
4	AV Camera	12V DC
5	External Fan	12V DC
6	DVD Screen	12V DC
7	All Parts	GND

4.6.4 Motor Controller Drive

A motor controller is a device or group of devices that serves to govern in some predetermined manner the performance of an electric motor. A motor controller might include a manual or automatic means for starting and stopping the motor, selecting forward or reverse rotation, selecting and regulating the speed, regulating or limiting the torque, and protecting against overloads and faults [61]. In the current project, a threaded steel rod connecting to a 12V DC motor is used to represent the

virtual welding electrode. Figure 4.19 shows the driver for the 12V DC motor; when the point A at high level and the point B in low level the motor will rotate forward while when the point A at low level and the point B in high level the motor will rotate backward.

Figure 4.19 the 12V DC motor controller

Chapter Five

BasVR 1.1 Software

5.1 Introduction

The BasVW 1.1 is a virtual welding machine designed and constructed in Basrah University, the prefix Bas referred to the Basrah University and the suffix VW referred to the Virtual Welding while the 1.1 referred to the machine version.

The BasVW 1.1 systems are virtual reality arc welding training simulators covered shielded metal arc welding processes. The software based training systems are educational tools designed to supplement and enhance traditional welding training. The produced system allow students to practice their welding technique in a simulated and immersive environment.

5.2 BasVW 1.1 Parts

The BasVW 1.1 virtual welding machine provided as training tool for shielded metal arc welding processes (SMAW), it consists of:

1. Welding Gun Simulator.
2. Welding Helmet.
3. Welding Environment (22" touch Screen).
4. Virtual Welding Software.

The above three parts will be explained in chapter five. Regarding to the Virtual Welding Software, it is written in VB.net 2010 language from Microsoft. The software is using the Microsoft windows application Graphics Device Interface (GDI+) and DirectX11 to draw 2D virtual welding processes.

5.3 BasVW 1.1 Requirements

The BasVW 1.1 can be compatible for all Microsoft Windows versions from Windows® XP but the recommended requirements to work this software in best situation can me mention here:

1. Computer Windows® 7 Professional or Higher.
2. Intel® Core™ i5 Quad Processor.

- 3. 4GB DDR Memory.
- 4. 60GB Solid State Hard Drive
- 5. High Powered Graphics Card
- 6. Monitor 22 inch LCD Touch Monitor
- 7. Input Power : 220V 50/60 Hz
- 8. Space of Dimensions: 90*150*45 cm

5.4 BasVW 1.1 Descriptions

The main form of the BasVW 1.1 System can be shown in figure 5.1. It is important to mention that before begin the virtual welding process; the user needs to prepare the virtual welding electrode, which is including in the Welding Gun Simulator. When the welding electrode not in "Full Electrode Length" the user must be push "Prepare" in 22" touch screen. In this case the welding electrode length will increases until it reached to the maximum electrode length. In this case, the user push "START"

Figure 5.1 The main page of the BasVW 1.1

The second step in this BasVW1.1 is to select the required welding data that is including as shown in figure 5.2:

- **Trainee Name**
- **Welding process;** four types of welding process data entered to the software as data base, these types including:
 - Stick or Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW).
 - MIG (Flux Cored) or Flux Cored Arc Welding (FCAW).
 - MIG (Solid Cored) or Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW).
 - TIG or Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW)
- **Welding Position;** the software covered all required welding positions, so it is including Practice Plate, 1G Flat Groove, 2F Horizontal Tee, 2G Horizontal Groove, 2G Schedule40, 2G XXS, 3F Vertical Tee, 3G Vertical Groove, 4F Overhead Tee, 4G Overhead Groove, 5G Schedule40, 5G XXS, 6G Schedule40 and 6G XXS
- **Material;** the system covered steel, mild steel and cast iron.
- **Electrode Size;** the software covered the most widely used welding electrodes so it is including:
 - E6010/E6011-3/32"(2.4mm)
 - E6010/E6011-1/8"(3.2mm)
 - E6010/E6011-5/32"(5.0mm)
 - E6010/E6011-3/16"(5.8mm)
 - E6010/E6011-7/32"(5.6mm)
 - E6010/E6011-1/4"(6.4mm)
 - E6013-1/16"(1.6mm)
 - E6013-5/64"(2.0mm)

- E6013-3/32"(2.4mm)
- E6013-1/8"(3.2mm)
- E6013-5/32"(5.0mm)
- E6013-3/16"(5.8mm)
- E6013-7/32"(5.6mm)
- E6013-1/4"(6.4mm)
- E6013-5/64"(2.0mm)
- E6014-1/8"(3.2mm)
- E6014-5/32"(5.0mm)
- E6014-3/16"(5.8mm)
- E6014-7/32"(5.6mm)
- E6014-1/4"(6.4mm)
- E6018-1/8"(3.2mm)
- E6018-5/32"(5.0mm)
- E6018-3/16"(5.8mm)
- E6018-7/32"(5.6mm)
- E6018-1/4"(6.4mm)

Form1

Trainer_Name XXX01

Welding_Process STICK

Welding_Position 0_Practice_Plate

Material Mild_Steel

Electrode_Size 6011-3/32 (2.4mm)

Welding Start

Figure 5.2 Primary welding process requirements in BasVW 1.1

The required position can be shown in three groups as shown in figure 5.3- 5.5. Figure 5.3 shows the Practice plate or 1F, 1G Flat Groove, 2F Horizontal Tee and 2G Horizontal Groove.

Figure 5.3 Virtual welding positions: a) Practice plat, b) 1G Flat Groove, c) 2F Horizontal Tee d) 2G Horizontal groove

Figure 5.4 shows the second positions group which including the 3F Vertical Tee, 3G Vertical Groove, 4F Overhead Tee and 4G Overhead Groove while figure 5.5 shows the high level group which including 5G suchuale40, 5G XXS, 6G Suchuale40 and 6G XXS.

Figure 5.4 Virtual welding positions: a) 3F Vertical Tee, b) 3G Vertical Groove, c) 4F Overhead Tee d) 4G Overhead Groove

Figure 5.5 Virtual welding positions: a) 5G suchuale40, b) 5G XXS, c) 6G Suchuale40, d) 6G XXS

As soon as the welding electrode touches the 22" screen, the virtual welding process will begin and the virtual welding process will draw. The main welding process will appear in the 22" touch screen and the helmet 8" screen.

The main welding parameters will sketch as soon as the virtual welding process finished. So that performances of the trainees in the below parameters will check.

- Welding Arc length.
- Welding travel angle.
- Welding working angle.
- Welding travel speed.

All procedures of BasVW 1.1 can be shown in program flow-chart as indicated in figure 5.6.

Figure 5.6 BasVW 1.1 flow-chart

5.5 BasVW 1.1 Program

The program was be written in VB.net with Visual Studio 2010 from Microsoft , the Software divided to several parts; at the beginning the software used all required libraries which are provided from VB.net besides to the libraries of Labjack U3 and Vectornav VN-100. The second part covered the virtual welding process welding while the third part was included the main requirements to calculate the virtual welding parameters such as welding angles and arc length distance.

5.5.1 Labjack Programming

In this section, the required Lablack HV U3 programing as ADC will be mentioned. At the beginning, the software verifies the compatibility of the Labjack to the PC system, this step will be given as error message as indicated below:

```
Imports LabJack.LabJackUD
Sub ErrorMessage(ByVal err As LabJackUDEException)
    MsgBox("Function returned LabJackUD Error #" & _
        Str$(err.LJUDError) & _
        " " & _
        err.ToString)
End Sub
```

Another Labjack programming steps will be mentioned in next sections such as using Labjack to control the helmet monitor and virtual welding electrode consumption behavior.

5.5.2 Welding Electrode Consumption Programming

The Labjack card supplies two pins as analog output, these two pins DAC0 and DAC1 are used to control the 12V DC motor with gear box and motor drive to represent the simulate welding electrode.

When the software beginning, the user needs to prepare the simulate welding electrode to be in full length, in this case, theDAC0 will be zero while the DAC1 will be 5V as indicated below:

```

Dim lngError As Integer
Dim lngHandle As Integer
Dim strError(255) As Char
Try
    LJUD.OpenLabJack(LJUD.DEVICE.U3, LJUD.CONNECTION.USB, "0", CBool(1),
lngHandle)
    'LJUD.ePut(u3.ljhandle, LJUD.IO.PIN_CONFIGURATION_RESET, 0, 0, 0);
Catch x As LabJackUDEException
    ErrorMessage(x)
    lngError = x.LJUDError
End Try
LJUD.ErrorToString(CType(lngError, LJUD.LJUDError), strError)

LJUD.eGet(lngHandle, LJUD.IO.PUT_ANALOG_ENABLE_PORT, 0, 3, 16)
' Electrode Consumption Effect, Backward On:5, off:0
LJUD.ePut(lngHandle, LJUD.IO.PUT_DAC, CType(0, LJUD.CHANNEL), 0, 0)
' Electrode Consumption Effect, Forward On:5, off:0
LJUD.ePut(lngHandle, LJUD.IO.PUT_DAC, CType(1, LJUD.CHANNEL), 5, 0)

```

When the virtual welding process begins, the simulate welding electrode length must be decreased as a real electrode consumption, so the process will reverse as mention below:

```

' Electrode Consumption Effect (DAC0), Backward On:5, off:0
LJUD.ePut(lngHandle, LJUD.IO.PUT_DAC, CType(0, LJUD.CHANNEL), 5, 0)
' Electrode Consumption Effect, (DAC1) ,Forward On:5, off:0
LJUD.ePut(lngHandle, LJUD.IO.PUT_DAC, CType(1, LJUD.CHANNEL), 0, 0)

```

When there is no any virtual welding process such as the arc length is out of the recommended values, and then both DAC0 and DAC1 will be zero as below:

```

' Electrode Consumption Effect (DAC0), Backword On:5, off:0
LJUD.ePut(lngHandle, LJUD.IO.PUT_DAC, CType(0, LJUD.CHANNEL), 0, 0)
' Electrode Consumption Effect, (DAC1) ,Forwardword On:5, off:0
LJUD.ePut(lngHandle, LJUD.IO.PUT_DAC, CType(1, LJUD.CHANNEL), 0, 0)

```

5.5.3 Inferred and Ultrasound Sensor Programming

The bins AIN1 and AIN2 are used to get the required ultrasound and inferred sensors respectively. The ultrasound and inferred (IR) sensors are used as displacement sensors to get the virtual welding travel speed. The

required code to get the values of ultrasound and inferred sensors can be shown below:

```
'Configure FIO0 and FIO1 as analog, all else as digital. That means
'we pass starting channel 0, a value of 3 (binary ...0011), and
'a number of bits of 16.
LJUD.eGet(IngHandle, LJUD.IO.PUT_ANALOG_ENABLE_PORT, 0, 3, 16)
'Get a reading from AIN1 for ultrasound sensor
LJUD.eGet(IngHandle, LJUD.IO.GET_AIN, CType(1, LJUD.CHANNEL), dblAIN1, 0)

'Get a reading from AIN2 for inferred sensor
LJUD.eGet(IngHandle, LJUD.IO.GET_AIN, CType(2, LJUD.CHANNEL), dblAIN2, 0)
```

5.5.4 LVDT Sensor Programming

The Labjack bin AIN0 used as input data to get the response value of the linear variable differential transformer (LVDT), when the LVDT sensor forces indirection of PC touch screen the value of the LVDT will be variable according to this value. The instantaneous value of LVDT will be send to the Labjack via bin AIN0 as indicated below:

```
LJUD.eGet(IngHandle, LJUD.IO.PUT_ANALOG_ENABLE_PORT, 0, 3, 16)
'Get a reading from AIN0.
LJUD.eGet(IngHandle, LJUD.IO.GET_AIN, 0, dblAIN0, 0)
```

5.5.5 Helmet Monitor Programming

When the value of LVDT sensor with recommended values which compatible within electrode diameter, the monitor in the helmet will be received data from PC as video via VGA to video convertor. In this case, the software will send a single to small conductor to change the helmet monitor data from VGA camera to virtual welding process from PC monitor. The system will be used AIN4 for this purpose by give it 5V as shown below:

```
' Hamelt PC/Camera Converter. On: Camera , Off: PC
LJUD.eGet(IngHandle, LJUD.IO.PUT_DIGITAL_BIT, CType(4, LJUD.CHANNEL), 1,
0)
```

When the LVDT values out of the recommended values, then the system will be given AIN4 pin a 0V as shown below:

```
' Hamelt PC/Camera Converter. On: Camera , Off: PC
```

```
LJUD.eGet(lngHandle, LJUD.IO.PUT_DIGITAL_BIT, CType(4, LJUD.CHANNEL), 0,
0)
```

5.5.6 Welding Angles Programming

To get the travel and working angle, the Vectornav VN-100 is used. The working angle and travel angle are corresponding to pitch and roll angles respectively. Vectornav DLL library will be used across COM3 with 9600 Hz frequency as shown below:

```
' Part Of VectorNave VN100
Imports VectorNav.Devices
Dim vn100 = New Vn100("COM3", 9600)
vn100.Connect()
Dim attitude = vn100.GetAttitude()
vn100.Disconnect()
' Travel Angle
Travel_Angle = Int(-0.0035 * Val(attitude.Ypr.RollInDegs) ^ 2 + 0.6733 *
Val(attitude.Ypr.RollInDegs) + 88.099)
' Working Angle
Working_Angle = Int(0.0002 * Val(attitude.Ypr.PitchInDegs) ^ 3 + 0.0073 *
Val(attitude.Ypr.PitchInDegs) ^ 2 + 1.1106 * Val(attitude.Ypr.PitchInDegs) + 69.677)
```

5.5.7 Welding Positions and Electrode Sizes Selection

All required positions are drawn as jpeg pictures and enter to the main program to select any position required. When the user prefers to get any position either for fillet or groove welding, he needs only to go to the selected list in the main page of the program and the program will be selected the simulate shape for the virtual welding process. The same way can be used to select the required welding electrode size as shown below:

```
' Part of Welding Drawing 1-2
If ComboBox1.Text = "0_Practice_Plate" Then
Dim b As New Bitmap("../0_Practice_Plate.JPG") 'Load an image that will be
used as a second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
b.MakeTransparent()
PictureBox1.Image = b
End If
If ComboBox1.Text = "2F_Horizontal_Tee" Then
Dim b As New Bitmap("../2F_Horizontal_Tee.JPG") 'Load an image that will
be used as a second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
b.MakeTransparent()
```

```
PictureBox1.Image = b
End If
If ComboBox1.Text = "2G_Horizontal_Groove" Then
    Dim b As New Bitmap("../2G_Horizontal_Groove.JPG")    'Load an image that
will be used as a second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
    b.MakeTransparent()
    PictureBox1.Image = b
End If

If ComboBox1.Text = "2G_Schedule40" Then
    Dim b As New Bitmap("../2G_Schedule40.JPG")    'Load an image that will be
used as a second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
    b.MakeTransparent()
    PictureBox1.Image = b
End If

If ComboBox1.Text = "2G_XXS" Then
    Dim b As New Bitmap("../2G_XXS.JPG")    'Load an image that will be used as a
second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
    b.MakeTransparent()
    PictureBox1.Image = b
End If

If ComboBox1.Text = "3G_Vertical_Groove" Then
    Dim b As New Bitmap("../3G_Vertical_Groove.JPG")    'Load an image that will
be used as a second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
    b.MakeTransparent()
    PictureBox1.Image = b
End If

If ComboBox1.Text = "3F_Vertical_Tee" Then
    Dim b As New Bitmap("../3F_Vertical_Tee.JPG")    'Load an image that will be
used as a second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
    b.MakeTransparent()
    PictureBox1.Image = b
End If

If ComboBox1.Text = "4F_Overhead_Tee" Then
    Dim b As New Bitmap("../4F_Overhead_Tee.JPG")    'Load an image that will be
used as a second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
    b.MakeTransparent()
    PictureBox1.Image = b
End If

If ComboBox1.Text = "4G_Overhead_Groove" Then
```

```

    Dim b As New Bitmap("../4G_Overhead_Groove.JPG")    'Load an image that
will be used as a second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
    b.MakeTransparent()
    PictureBox1.Image = b
End If

If ComboBox1.Text = "5G_Schedule40" Then
    Dim b As New Bitmap("../5G_Schedule40.JPG")    'Load an image that will be
used as a second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
    b.MakeTransparent()
    PictureBox1.Image = b
End If

If ComboBox1.Text = "5G_XXS" Then
    Dim b As New Bitmap("../5G_XXS.JPG")    'Load an image that will be used as a
second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
    b.MakeTransparent()
    PictureBox1.Image = b
End If

If ComboBox1.Text = "6G_Schedule40" Then
    Dim b As New Bitmap("../6G_Schedule40.JPG")    'Load an image that will be
used as a second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
    b.MakeTransparent()
    PictureBox1.Image = b
End If

If ComboBox1.Text = "G_XXS" Then
    Dim b As New Bitmap("../G_XXS.JPG")    'Load an image that will be used as a
second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
    b.MakeTransparent()
    PictureBox1.Image = b
End If

```

5.5.8 Virtual Welding Drawing Programming

The GDI library from Microsoft Windows is used to simulate welding process in shielded metal arc welding (SMAW). The graphic library is provided several options to select the continue lines such as the color and size. In current software, a grey color is used to represent the virtual welding process. The tip of the simulate electrode in welding gun can be worked as a mouse, when the simulate electrode touch the PC screen the welding process will be begun and the virtual process drawing will be started as shown below:

```

Imports System.Drawing
Dim penColr As Pen = New Pen(Color.Gray, 3)
Dim fuzzPen() As Pen = {New Pen(Color.FromArgb(128, penColr.Color), 3 * fuzzsize),
    New Pen(Color.FromArgb(160, Color.Green), 3 * fuzzsize),
    New Pen(Color.FromArgb(128, Color.Red), 3 * fuzzsize),
    New Pen(Color.FromArgb(128, Color.Blue), 3 * fuzzsize)}
Dim SelectedFuzzPen As Integer
Dim b As New Bitmap("../scratch2.jpg")    'Load an image that will be used as a
second layer, above the background, but below the dynamic drawing
b.MakeTransparent()
PictureBox1.Image = b
gfullmap = BufferedGraphicsManager.Current
fullmap = gfullmap.Allocate(PictureBox1.CreateGraphics, PictureBox1.ClientRectangle)
fuzzmap = New Bitmap(CInt(PictureBox1.ClientSize.Width \ CLng(fuzzsize)) + 1,
CInt(PictureBox1.ClientSize.Height \ CLng(fuzzsize)) + 1)
gfuzzmap = Graphics.FromImage(fuzzmap)
gfuzzmap.SmoothingMode = Drawing2D.SmoothingMode.AntiAlias

fullmap.Graphics.SmoothingMode = Drawing2D.SmoothingMode.AntiAlias
gfuzzmap.ScaleTransform(1 / fuzzsize, 1 / fuzzsize)

Private Sub PictureBox1_MouseMove(ByVal sender As Object, ByVal e As
System.Windows.Forms.MouseEventArgs) Handles PictureBox1.MouseMove
' Part of Welding Drawing 1-3 ' Mouse positions
Static lx, ly As Integer
If e.Button = Windows.Forms.MouseButtons.Left Then
fullmap.Graphics.DrawLine(penColr, lx, ly, e.X, e.Y)
gfuzzmap.DrawLine(fuzzPen(SelectedFuzzPen), lx, ly, e.X, e.Y)
PictureBox1.Invalidate()
End If
lx = e.X
ly = e.Y
Label2.Text = CStr(Val(lx))
Label3.Text = CStr(Val(ly))
End Sub

```

5.5.9 Export Virtual Welding Process to Excel Sheet

In order to make an online saving for virtual welding process, all data will be sent to excel sheet. Position of the welding electrode , working angle, travel angle, ultrasound displacement , inferred displacement, welding arc length , motor revelations , and virtual welding time can be consider as the selected saved values. The software cab be able to save 99 trainees data.

```

' Part of Excel Sheet 1-2
cn.SetExcelConnectionString(IO.Path.Combine(Application.StartupPath, "File1.xls"),
UseHeader.Yes, ExcelImex.TryScan)
Dim cmd As OleDbCommand = New OleDbCommand("SELECT X_Axes, Y_Axes,
Working_Angle ,Travel_Angle, U_Sound, Arc_Length, Turn_No, IR, W_Time FROM
[Sheet1$]", cn)
ExcelAdapter.SelectCommand = cmd
cn.Open()
ExcelAdapter.Fill(DataSet1, "Sheet1")
bsData.DataSource = DataSet1.Tables("Sheet1").DefaultView

' DataGridView1.DataSource = bsData
ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand = New OleDbCommand With
{
.CommandText = "INSERT INTO [Sheet1$]
VALUES(@P1,@P2,@P3,@P4,@P5,@P6,@P7,@P8,@P9)",
.Connection = cn
}
' Read X_Axes
ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters.Add(
New OleDbParameter With
{
.ParameterName = "@P1",
.OleDbType = OleDbType.WChar
}
)

'Read Y_Axes,
ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters.Add(
New OleDbParameter With
{
.ParameterName = "@P2",
.OleDbType = OleDbType.WChar
}
)

'Read Working_Angle ,
ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters.Add(
New OleDbParameter With
{
.ParameterName = "@P3",
.OleDbType = OleDbType.WChar
}
)
' Read Travel_Angle,
ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters.Add(

```

```
New OleDbParameter With
{
    .ParameterName = "@P4",
    .OleDbType = OleDbType.WChar
}
)

' Read U_Sound,
ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters.Add(
    New OleDbParameter With
    {
        .ParameterName = "@P5",
        .OleDbType = OleDbType.WChar
    }
)

' Read Arc_Length,
ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters.Add(
    New OleDbParameter With
    {
        .ParameterName = "@P6",
        .OleDbType = OleDbType.WChar
    }
)

' Read Turn_No
ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters.Add(
    New OleDbParameter With
    {
        .ParameterName = "@P7",
        .OleDbType = OleDbType.WChar
    }
)

' Read IR
ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters.Add(
    New OleDbParameter With
    {
        .ParameterName = "@P8",
        .OleDbType = OleDbType.WChar
    }
)

' Read W_Time
ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters.Add(
    New OleDbParameter With
```

```
{
    .ParameterName = "@P9",
    .OleDbType = OleDbType.WChar
}
)
' Part of Excel Sheet 1-3 ' Excel File updated Data
  If Not String.IsNullOrEmpty(Label2.Text) AndAlso Not
String.IsNullOrEmpty(Label3.Text) Then
    ' X-Axes position
    ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters(0).Value = Val(Label2.Text)
    ' Y Axes Position
    ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters(1).Value = Val(Label3.Text)
    ' Working Angle
    ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters(2).Value = Int(-0.0035 *
Val(attitude.Ypr.RollInDegs) ^ 2 + 0.6733 * Val(attitude.Ypr.RollInDegs) + 88.099)
    ' Travel Angle
    ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters(3).Value = Int(0.0002 *
Val(attitude.Ypr.PitchInDegs) ^ 3 + 0.0073 * Val(attitude.Ypr.PitchInDegs) ^ 2 + 1.1106 *
Val(attitude.Ypr.PitchInDegs) + 69.677)
    ' Ultrasound Displacement
    ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters(4).Value = Val(dblAIN0)
    ' Arc_Length
    ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters(5).Value = Val(dblAIN1)
    ' Turn_No
    ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters(6).Value = Val(dblAIN2)
    ' IR
    ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters(7).Value = Val(dblAIN3)
    ' Time
    ExcelAdapter.InsertCommand.Parameters(8).Value = Val(TimeOfDay)
```

Chapter Six

Results and Discussions

CHAPTER SIX

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results and discussions will be divided into two parts; welding sensors calibration and virtual welding case studies.

The welding sensors calibration will be included:

1. Welding angles sensors.
2. Welding arc length sensor.
3. Welding travel speed sensors.
4. Welding electrode consumption.

In the second part, there are six case studies will be discussed; these case studies are included:

1. Straight Bead on Flat plate.
2. Welding Pad on Flat Plate.
3. Flat Groove (1G) and Horizontal Groove (2G).
4. Tee Joint Horizontal Position (2F).
5. Tee Joint Vertical Position (3F).
6. Tee Joint Overhead Position (4F).

In the third part of results, the effect of using image processing in virtual welding are studied.

6.1 Welding Sensors Calibration

6.1.1 Welding Angles Sensors Calibration

The rotation angles Yaw, Roll and Pitch which get from VectorNav VN-100 can be used to get welding angles; travel angle and working angle. According to the arrangement of the VN100 in the welding simulated gun, two of these angles are used. From Vectornav Pitch and Roll are used to get working angle and travel angle respectively.

Several of Experiments on the Vectornav tested to get the required angles values. The variation of the Pitch angle is used as a function of the working angle. Table 6.1 indicates five tests on pitch angle to get working angle.

Table 6.1 Vectornav VN-100 Data to get Working Angle

Working Angle(°)	Pitch Angle Readings from Vectornav VN-100					
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	Average
0	-80	-73	-79	-78	-83	-78.6
10	-66	-62	-60	-62	-68	-63.6
20	-53	-50	-46	-48	-56	-50.6
30	-38	-38	-33	-35	-69	-42.6
40	-27	-23	-21	-21	-29	-24.2
50	-15	-9	-10	-10	-19	-12.6
60	-4	4	0	-2	-8	-2
70	9	12	8	6	3	7.6
80	16	16	13	15	16	15.2
90	19	21	21	20	22	20.6

Figure 6.1 shows the relationship between the pitch angle and working angle.

Figure 6.1 Relations between working angle and pitch angle

A polynomial curve fitting used to find the relationships between the average pitch angles and the required working welding angles as below:

$$\text{Working Angle} = 0.003\theta^3 + 0.0073\theta^2 + 1.034\theta + 64.025 \quad (6.1)$$

Where θ represents the pitch. The resulted equation gave good results with real welding angle with R^2 equal to 0.9945 where R^2 is computed from the sum of the squares of the distances of the points from the best-fit curve.

By the same way, the travel angle is got from the Roll angle, also five tests reading is used to get average reading. The relation between the welding travel angle and the Roll angle is given in figure 6.2

Figure 6.2 Relations between working angle and pitch angle

A polynomial curve fitting is used to the required welding travel angle.

$$\text{Travel Angle} = 00021\emptyset^2 - 0.9421\emptyset - 13.804 \quad (6.2)$$

Where \emptyset represents the Roll angle. The resulted equation gave good results with real welding angle with R^2 equal to 0.9995.

From these results, the Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) (Vectornav VN-100) which used accelerometer, gyroscopes and magnetometers to get rotation angle in current project consider a good tool to get working and travel welding angles with accepted approach. This approach will be used in next sections to teach new trainee the accepted welding angles.

6.1.2 Welding Arc Length Calibration

A Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVTD) sensor is used to study the effect of welding arc length. The welding arc length is a major important since it is limited the nature of the result welding layer and the spatters. The output voltage is compared with vernier measurement to get the displacement; the tested data is shown in table 6.2

Table 6.2 LVDT Output Voltage Readings

Distance(mm)	LVDT Output Voltage readings							
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	Average
8	5.55	5.5	5.5	5.51	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.508571
7	4.75	4.49	4.78	4.44	4.42	4.72	4.63	4.604286
6	3.9	3.8	3.57	3.51	3.73	3.64	3.96	3.73
5	3.03	2.81	2.83	2.83	2.81	2.84	2.75	2.842857
4	2.09	1.95	1.83	1.49	1.5	1.5	1.77	1.732857
3	0.86	1.07	0.81	0.47	0.6	0.66	0.55	0.717143
2	-0.1	-0.148	-0.1	-0.14	-1.1	-0.16	-0.16	-0.27257
1	-1.21	-1.2	-0.93	-1.5	-1.18	-1.12	-1.17	-1.18714
0	-1.81	-1.81	-1.8	-1.82	-1.81	-1.81	-1.82	-1.81143

Figure 6.3 indicates the variation of the arc length relative to the LVDT output voltage.

Figure 6.3 Relation between welding arc length and output voltage of LVDT sensor.

A polynomial calibration equation can be given to get the required distance from the output voltage of LVDT.

$$\text{Arc Length}(\text{distance}) = -0.004x^2 + 1.0711x + 2.1542 \quad (6.3)$$

Where x represent the LVDT output voltage,

The resulted equation gives a good approach for the real arc welding effect, where the displacement varies between 0 mm and 5 mm that is accepted with most Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) processes where the recommended value closed with welding electrode diameter

[1]. In training courses the trainees widely used on welding electrode where the welding electrode diameter do not exceed the 5 mm.

Because of the low change between the maximum and minimum values of the welding arc length, there is a difficult to represent this change in the virtual environments, so that the resulted data from LVDT can be considered one of the advantages of the current project where all ultrasound and infrared sensors failed to represent the arc welding length. Although of the success of laser sensor to represent the arc welding length but their cost is very expensive, so that the LVDT sensor data is accepted as compared between the response to the representation and the cost.

6.1.3 Travel Speed Sensor Calibration

One of the disadvantages of both Infrared and ultrasound sensors, is a dead region where the sensor does not able to recognize the nearest places to the sensor which is about 8-10 cm, so although the low cost of such sensors but the problems of dead region can be limited the using of such sensors. Since the current project depending upon minimize the whole cost to the lowest price so that the using of such sensors considers as a necessary. In order to overcome the problem of dead region a reflecting wall constructs to reflect the signals of both sensor. MaxSonar®EZ4™ (see appendix E) is used as ultrasound range finder sensor while GP2D120XJ00F used as infrared proximity sensor, the purpose of using both sensors is to get the best sensor performance to the construction model.

After the calibration the below equations are obtained:

For GP2D120XJ00F infrared sensor:

$$IR \text{ Displacement} = (0.528(Output \ Voltage)) + 8.067 \quad (6.4)$$

For MaxSonar®EZ4™ ultrasound sensor:

$$EZ4 \text{ Displacement} = (29.218(Output \ Voltage))^{(-1.159)} \quad (6.5)$$

6.1.4. Welding Electrode Consumption Calibration

The total length of the constructed rod is 30 cm compatible to the E6010 Carbon Steel Electrode, the electrode is moving in both directions;

forward and backward. In backward stroke, the virtual welding occurs while the forward stroke simulated new welding electrode replacement.

An optical rotary encoder with Labjack HV U3 are used to record the 12V DC motor pluses, the virtual welding system designed to read pulses on each 20 ms for 10 ms. The total number of pulses is divided by the total welding electrode length when the electrode from position in length 0 cm to position in length 30 cm and vice versa.

When the trainer prefer to weld and the arc length in accepted range (measured by LVTD sensor) the software send a signal to the DC motor to rotate in backward direction and the welding electrode length begin to decrease till:

- The trainer stops the power to the welding simulated gun.
- The arc length which measured by LVTD became out of work range.
- The welding electrode length reaches to the 0 cm position.

6.2 Training and Validating Case Studies

The study course including five trainees, each trainee working on six case studies, on each case study there are four tests, on each test there are four welding parameters are studied; travel angle, working angle, travel speed and welding arc length are studied.

In the current discussions, results of three students will be discussed, in the first case only the behavior of first student will be studied while in rest cases the results of three students will be discussed while the other data will be saved in the system that is able to save 100 trainees tests.

6.2.1 Case 1: Straight Bead on Flat Plate

In this case a plate material Mild Steel of thickness of 3/16" (4.8 mm) and a single process of E6013-1/8"(3.2mm) electrode are used to represent the virtual welding process.

Table 6.3 shows the first attempt of the trainee no.1; the welding distance, welding working angle, welding travel speed and welding arc length are shown.

Table 6.3 First Attempt on Flat Plate with E6013 Electrode

Time(s)	Distance(cm) (screen)	Distance(cm) (Ultrasound)	Distance(cm) (Infrared)	Working Angle(°)	Travel Angle(°)	Arc Length (mm)
1.00	1.34	1.78	1.45	41.00	49.00	0.58
2.00	1.55	2.05	1.67	41.00	49.00	3.06
3.00	1.79	2.37	1.93	29.00	46.00	3.68
4.00	2.03	2.37	2.05	29.00	45.00	1.20
5.00	2.52	2.93	2.53	30.00	44.00	0.59
6.00	2.76	3.21	2.78	28.00	44.00	1.70
7.00	3.00	3.78	3.15	29.00	43.00	1.90
8.00	3.45	4.34	3.62	29.00	43.00	2.09
9.00	4.66	5.87	4.89	28.00	41.00	1.17
10.00	4.90	6.17	5.15	28.00	42.00	0.85
11.00	5.52	6.95	5.80	28.00	41.00	0.74
12.00	6.34	7.99	6.67	28.00	40.00	0.88
13.00	6.79	8.56	7.14	27.00	38.00	0.66
14.00	7.24	9.12	7.61	26.00	36.00	0.59
15.00	7.76	9.78	8.15	26.00	34.00	0.58
16.00	7.76	9.78	8.15	27.00	35.00	0.74
17.00	8.21	10.34	8.62	27.00	32.00	1.16
18.00	8.45	10.64	8.88	41.00	22.00	1.49
19.00	9.14	11.51	9.60	41.00	23.00	0.66
20.00	9.66	12.17	10.15	41.00	25.00	0.87
21.00	10.59	13.34	11.13	30.00	22.00	1.28
22.00	10.83	13.64	11.38	41.00	24.00	0.87
23.00	11.55	14.56	12.14	30.00	23.00	0.59
24.00	13.21	16.64	13.88	30.00	23.00	0.61
25.00	13.45	16.94	14.13	30.00	23.00	0.75
26.00	14.14	17.81	14.86	30.00	23.00	0.58
27.00	14.79	18.64	15.55	30.00	21.00	0.76
28.00	15.59	19.64	16.38	30.00	23.00	0.58
29.00	16.28	20.51	17.10	30.00	23.00	1.10
30.00	17.59	22.16	18.48	30.00	22.00	1.46
31.00	19.41	24.46	20.40	30.00	19.00	0.58
32.00	19.83	24.98	20.84	30.00	19.00	0.73
33.00	20.07	25.29	21.09	30.00	19.00	1.96
34.00	20.52	25.85	21.56	29.00	16.00	2.74
35.00	21.03	26.50	22.11	30.00	19.00	2.48
36.00	21.72	27.37	22.83	29.00	15.00	3.10
37.00	22.21	27.98	23.34	29.00	15.00	3.38
38.00	22.69	26.14	22.71	29.00	15.00	3.18
39.00	23.10	26.62	23.12	29.00	17.00	3.27
40.00	23.97	27.61	23.98	28.00	14.00	3.48

41.00	24.10	27.77	24.12	29.00	15.00	3.26
42.00	25.31	29.16	25.33	28.00	15.00	2.10
43.00	25.52	29.40	25.53	29.00	16.00	2.43
44.00	26.21	30.19	26.22	28.00	14.00	2.80
45.00	26.48	32.73	27.54	29.00	15.00	2.13
46.00	27.21	33.63	28.29	29.00	15.00	2.11
47.00	27.69	34.22	28.79	28.00	13.00	3.37
48.00	28.00	34.61	29.11	28.00	12.00	2.39

6.2.1.1 Effect of Welding Travel Speed

There is a direct method to get the welding travel speed; there are three approaches depending on divide the resulted welding distance to the time interval. So to find the welding travel speed, the required welding distance must be estimated. In current project three tools are used to get the welding distance; the first which is obtained from ultrasound sensor and the second which obtained from infrared sensor while the third depending upon analyzing the picture of the virtual welding view. In the third method the simulated welding electrode worked as a mouse , when it touch the 22" Screen the system indicated it position and when it is moved to the another position the system also indicated the new position , so there is ability to find the difference between the two positions. It is easy to get a proportion between the real dimensions of the 22" screen and the current picture of virtual welding view, so the dimensions which are obtained from the third method is a real dimensions.

Figure 6.4 indicates the change of distance of the welding from 0 to 28 (see table 6.3) by using three methods, ultrasound and infrared sensors and (image analysis).

Figure 6.4 Welding distance measurement by using ultrasound and infrared and screen analysis

The change of the welding distance in ultrasound is large than the distance change which measured by infrared and by using direct method by screen analysis. The reason may be belong to the nature of this type since it is commercial one (less than 10\$), while the infrared is about 50\$.

In general, both ultrasound and infrared are used at the beginning of this project, but finally the using of touch screen coordinates and consider simulated electrode as a mouse, so the screen coordinate will be used in the next sections.

In the first case study the trainee or student, learn to run a straight bead on flat plate. It is important to mention here that the software provide 14 welding positions. The system cover Practice Plate, 1G Flat Groove, 2F Horizontal Tee, 2G Horizontal Groove, 2G Schedule40, 2G XXS, 3F Vertical Tee, 3G Vertical Groove, 4F Overhead Tee, 4G Overhead Groove, 5G Schedule40, 5G XXS, 6G Schedule40 and 6G XXS, while the current discussions covered only four positions Practice Plate, 1G Flat Groove, 2F Horizontal Tee, 3F Vertical Tee, and 4F Overhead Tee.

Figures 6.5-6.8 indicate the four attempts on virtual welding process of the trainee no.1, the welding parameters changes will be discussed in next section. Figure 6.5 shows a bad welding process with high welding travel speed, the trainee developed his skill in the second attempt and reduced

the travel speed as indicated in figure 6.6 but the welding process stills listed within a bad welding process. In the figure 6.7 and 6.8 the welding process is became quite good.

Although figures 6.6-6.8 give the user primary view about the trainees performance but it is not indicated the correct values of the welding angles, travel speed and welding arc length, which will be discussed in next sections.

Figure 6.5 First attempt on Straight bead flat plate for trainee no.1

Figure 6.6 Second attempt on Straight bead flat plate trainee no.1

Figure 6.7 Third attempt on Straight bead flat plate for trainee no.1

Figure 6.8 Fourth attempt on Straight bead flat plate for trainee no.1

6.2.1.2 Effect of Working Angles on Flat Plate Welding

Since the time interval is different between four attempts so that the ability to study all four cases in one graph is limited. Figure 6.9 indicates the variation of working angle in the first attempt.

Figure 6.9 Working angle variation during the first attempt for trainee no.1

Since it is a first attempt, so that there is a large change in travel angles is occurred such as between 15° and 30° that are far from the recommended values 40° - 45° [56].

In the next attempts, the trainee working angle performance is developed rapidly, in the fourth attempt, the trainee reached to good accepted values.

Table 6.4 indicates the measured working angle of the trainee no 1 in the last three attempts during the period from 10-20 s from the virtual welding process. The recommended angle used as 45 [56].

Table 6.4 Working angle variation to the recommend value

Time(s)	2 nd Attempt		3 rd Attempt		4 th Attempt	
	Measured Angle	Discrepancy %	Measured Angle	Discrepancy %	Measured Angle	Discrepancy %
10	35	22	35	22	45	0
10.5	35	22	36	20	44	2
11	36	20	36	20	44	2
11.5	36	20	35	22	43	4
12	35	22	35	22	43	4
12.5	35	22	35	22	43	4
13	34	24	35	22	44	2
13.5	34	24	36	20	44	2
14	34	24	36	20	45	0
14.5	34	24	36	20	44	2

15	35	22	34	24	44	2
15.5	35	22	34	24	44	2
16	35	22	34	24	43	4
16.5	35	22	35	22	43	4
17	36	20	35	22	43	4
17.5	39	13	35	22	43	4
18	39	13	35	22	44	2
18.5	39	13	35	22	44	2
19	38	15	35	22	44	2
19.5	39	13	35	22	44	2
20	40	11	34	24	43	4

The equation of the discrepancy is:

$$\text{Working Angle discrepancy} = \frac{\text{Abs}(\text{Recommended Value} - \text{Measured Value})}{\text{Recommended Value}} * 100$$

Table 6.4 indicates the discrepancy reached to 0 which mean the trainee reached to a good score on straight bead flat plate, the system provide a sound alarm to the trainee when user is far to the recommended values, this alarm may be consider as the reason beyond the development in the trainee performance.

6.2.1.3 Effect of the Travel Angle

The trainee performance in the travel angle did not different to the performance of the working angle, the performance begins with bad results but it is reached to the recommended values in the last time interval.

Figure 6.10 Travel angle variation during the third attempt for trainee no.1

Figure 6.10 indicates the variation of the travel angle with time interval. In the first 20s, the welding travel angle is far from the recommended values of 5°-20°[62], but after this period the trainee performance became better, the trainee entered the recommended region and still in this region till the end of the virtual welding process. The sound alarm helped the trainee to enter the recommended region.

Although most of the time interval with recommended travel angle but there is, an oscillation in the values of these angles that means there is no stability in trainee hand which added to the high sensitivity of the Vectornav sensor to the change of the roll. In general, in spite of this oscillation of the travel angle, the variation is accepted and does not affect the use of Vectornav to find the welding angle.

6.2.1.4 Effect of the Travel Speed

There is no an active method to get the travel speed of the trainees in the Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW), but there is overall way by calculate the travel speed by dividing the whole welding length to the time interval of the welding process.

According to this method, table 6.5 shows the results of the four attempts of the trainee no.1.

Table 6.5 Overall travel speed values on the first case study

Attempt	Welding Distance(cm)	Welding Time(s)	travel speed (cm/s)
1	30	46	0.652
2	30	126	0.238
3	30	114	0.263
4	30	153	0.196

Table 6.5 shows the trainee no.1 began with high travel speed and then reduced his speed in second and third attempts but the travel speed still high until the fourth attempt when the trainee reduces the travel speed to the accepted value. It is important to mention here, there is no any recommended values for welding travel speed [1], it is depending on the type of plate flat or groove, diameter of the welding electrode, welding current and dimensions of the welding region area.

In current project, also another two welding travel speed indicators are studied, the first depending on finding the travel speed at each point on the welding workpiece and the another one depending on the whole view of the virtual welding process after finishing the process.

In first method, the travel speed calculates directly by using the formula shown below at any time.

$$\text{Travel Speed} = \frac{dx}{dt}$$

Where dx is the difference between the current position and the previous position of the welding electrode while dt is the difference between the current time and the previous time of the welding process.

Although the principal is correct but it gives a good results in welding process, since in welding processes, the welding do not occur as pure straight, it is occur on shapes of C, T, J, V, zigzag, ...etc. (see figure 6.11 [1]).

Figure 6.11 Recommended welding process movements [1]

Form figure 6.11, at any time, the beginning current position value form the reference of the welding process begins may be lower than the previous position that will give a mistake travel speed value. In general, this method will not be used in next case studies.

The second method is by using the whole view of virtual welding process, the whole view shows the accepted decision to tell the welding travel speed is fast , low or accepted, it is depending upon the width of the virtual welding in the result picture (see figures 6.5-6.8). Figure 6.5 shows the travel speed of the trainee varies from an accepted value at the beginning and then the travel speed is fast at the middle and return to the accepted value in the last region.

In next case studies, the indicator of the virtual welding picture will be used to examine the travel speed of the trainees while the other methods will not use.

6.2.1.5 Effect of the Welding Arc length

Length of the arc in Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) is a major parameter in welding process, it is affected on the shape of the welding and finishing of the workpiece, when the arc is too low, the electrode may be stick on the workpiece while when it is too high the spatters will spread on the surface.

The feedback signal from the LVDT is used as an indicator to the arc welding length, so a two guidelines is used to help the trainee to enter the recommended values as mentioned in chapter four (see Figure 4.10).

Figure 6.12 Variation of welding arc length with times

Figure 6.12 indicates the variation of the welding arc length with time and compares the actual values with the recommended values. The recommended value of the arc length is compatible with the welding electrode diameter [1]. In the current case study an E6013-1/8"(3.2mm) is used as a welding electrode, so that the recommended arc length will be 3.2 mm (Red Line) in figure 6.12. The performance of the trainee developed in the last 25 s , this may be belong to the notice of the guide lines in main welding process, so the oscillation is minimized to the accepted value.

In general, at the end of the first case discussions, the skills of the trainee no.1 are developed, the same thing occurs to the other four trainees, which lead to say, "The virtual welding training is a good tool as primary teaching for welding training courses". The virtual welding system enables the trainee to acquire the welding motion by practicing several exercises through a progressive learning embedded in the training process, so that by spending only 1 hour per day on this system, the trainees acquire the good gesture quicker and save more quantities of raw material.

6.2.2 Case 2: Welding Pad on Flat Plate

In this case a plate material Mild Steel with thickness of 3/16" (4.8 mm) and a single process with electrode of E6013-1/8"(3.2mm) is used to represent the virtual welding process.

In this case study, third attempt for three trainees is selected; the overall view from the first trainee is shown in figure 6.13.

Figure 6.13 Third attempt of trainee no.1 on welding pad case study

In the figure 6.13, a development increased gradually, where in the first welding line from the top corner, the welding process is rapid and oscillated, while in the second and third lines, the welding processes are inline and the travel speeds are accepted.

The benefit of virtual training system can be noticed clearly here, where the trainee can able to make several attempts till reach to the accepted score without any loss for materials.

The third attempt of the trainee no.2 can be shown in figure 6.14

Figure 6.14 Third attempt of trainee no.2 on welding pad case study

Although the virtual welding process is developed in the second line, but there is a decline in performance in the third line. In this case, the trainer told from the trainee to repeat the case study, in the repeated attempt the performance is very developed as shown in figure 6.15

Figure 6.15 Repeated of the third attempt of trainee no.2 on welding pad

The result of the trainee no.3 can be shown for the third attempt in the figure 6.16, where the trainee began from the tip of the lower right corner and continue up in the other welding lines in the pad.

Figure 6.16 Third attempt of trainee no.3 on welding pad

In overall view, the travel speed is accepted and there is a closed in welding lines where the distance between each two welding lines is accepted which lead to the ability to add new welding line.

6.2.2.1 Effect of Welding Parameters in Welding Pad

As mentioned in the last case study, the major welding parameters are working angle, travel angle, welding arc length and travel speed. The travel speed parameter is studied in the last section according to the overall view of welding process on welding pad for all three trainees.

Regarding to the other three parameters, to study the effect of each parameter for each trainee , about 27 figures is required since the welding time is different, so to minimize the figures number and to get overall view for all trainees in same time, an interval of time will be selected. The time intervals between 10-20 s. Furthermore the study will include the effect of the welding parameters change during the second welding line in the pad, which mean the effect of the first welding line and third welding line will not discussed. Although many cases will not discussed here but the user can be reach to them at any time since the system can be able to save data of 100 trainees.

6.2.2.2 Effect of Working Angle

The effect of the working angle change with time for three trainees during the time interval between 10-20 s can be shown in figure 6.17.

Figure 6.17 Variation of working angle with time of three trainees

Although all trainees in the recommended angles between 40° - 45° , the stability of the trainee no.3 can be noticed, while there is an oscillation in the performance of the trainee no.3, in this case the trainer can be told the trainee to develop his performance with new several trails till the trainee overcome the oscillation in working angle. In this case, the trainee will not need to attend the trainer in repeated attempts since the trainee can use the system output as a validation score. Regarding to the trainee no.2 the performance is accepted.

6.2.2.3 Effect of Travel Angle

To study the travel angle effect, the same method will be used to get the trainees' performance during 10-20 s intervals. Figure 6.18 shows the variation of travel angle with time during this interval.

Figure 6.18 Variation of working angle with time of three trainees

In figure 6.18, all trainees working with accepted angles between 20° and 30°, which means that a good development occurred in trainees' performance, so by spending only 1 hour per day on this system, the trainees acquire the good gesture quicker and save more of raw material. Furthermore, according to the wide range of recommended travel angles, the oscillation of the results with 1°-3° is accepted.

6.2.2.4 Effect of Welding Arc Length

Regarding welding arc length, the trainees' performance can be indicated in table 6.6, since the electrode E6013-1/8"(3.2mm) is used during this case study, so that the accepted arc length must be closed with this value. An arc length percentage error equation will be used to get the performance of the three trainees during the 10-20s interval, both the first and the fourth attempts for each trainee are studied.

The equation of the welding arc length percentage discrepancy can be given by:

$$\text{Arc Length discrepancy} = \frac{\text{Abs}(\text{Recommended Value} - \text{Measured Value})}{\text{Recommended Value}} * 100$$

Table 6.6 Percentage Error of the welding arc length for three trainees

Time(s)	Trainee no.1 discrepancy %		Trainee no.2 discrepancy %		Trainee no.3 discrepancy %	
	1 st Attempt	4 th Attempt	1 st Attempt	4 th Attempt	1 st Attempt	4 th Attempt
10.00	6.25	9.37	3.13	11.94	9.37	3.12
10.50	6.25	9.37	3.13	13.90	9.37	3.12
11.00	21.88	6.25	14.06	6.25	6.25	3.12
11.50	37.50	6.25	31.25	6.25	6.25	3.12
12.00	37.50	9.37	31.25	6.25	6.25	3.12
12.50	37.50	12.50	15.63	6.25	6.25	3.12
13.00	6.25	6.25	15.63	6.25	6.25	3.12
13.50	25.00	6.25	29.69	6.25	6.25	3.12
14.00	25.00	6.25	43.75	6.25	6.25	3.12
14.50	40.63	6.25	43.75	3.13	6.25	3.12
15.00	25.00	6.25	43.75	6.25	6.25	3.12
15.50	25.00	3.12	15.63	3.12	6.25	3.12
16.00	25.00	9.37	12.50	6.25	6.25	3.12
16.50	21.88	9.37	34.06	3.12	6.25	6.25
17.00	21.88	6.25	34.06	6.25	6.25	6.25
17.50	21.88	12.50	34.06	3.12	9.37	6.25
18.00	21.88	9.37	34.06	3.12	9.37	6.25
18.50	18.75	9.37	30.63	3.12	6.25	6.25
19.00	12.50	9.37	23.75	3.12	6.25	6.25
19.50	12.50	9.37	23.75	3.12	6.25	6.25
20.00	9.37	6.25	20.31	3.13	6.25	6.25
Min Error	6.25	3.12	3.13	3.12	6.25	3.12
Max. Error	40.63	12.50	43.75	13.90	9.37	6.25

During the selected time interval, the trainee no.1 performance developed from first attempt and fourth attempts where the maximum percentage error degrees from 40.63% in first attempt to 12.50%. In this case where the maximum percentage error do not reach to excepted value less than 10%, the trainee must be repeated his attempts till reached to the accepted value.

Also the maximum arc length percentage error of the trainee no.2 in the fourth attempts is about is 13.90%, but his attempt is accepted since there is a noticed development in the performance between the first attempt and the fourth attempt and the error values in fourth attempt from 11-20 s interval is accepted with 10%.

The performance of the trainee no.3 is accepted in both attempts which mean that the trainee begin to be compatible with virtual training and there is no need to more trials in this case study.

At the end of case study no.2, it is useful to mention here that the current project is a multi-purpose and can be used to teach a variety of exercises to up to 10 trainees per day.

6.2.3 Case 3: Flat Groove (1G) and Horizontal Groove (2G)

In this case two types of welding positions are used:

- 1G Flat Groove
- 2G Horizontal Groove

Groove welds are made in the space between two sections of metal. With the exception of the square-groove and flare-groove joints, one or more of the members being joined is prepared by removing metal to form a V-, J-, or U-shaped trough. This joint preparation provides for deeper or full penetration of the weld into the joint and provides clearance for the electrode.

In both positions a plate material Mild Steel 10 gauge with a single process with electrode of E6010/E6011-1/8"(3.2mm) are used to represent the virtual welding process, the results of trainee no.2 in the second attempt will discussed here.

6.2.3.1 Welding Parameters Effect on 1G Flat Groove

On 1G flat groove, the whole view of the resulted virtual welding is shown in figure 6.19.

Figure 6.19 Virtual welding view of 1G Flat Groove

Figure 6.19 shows the travel speed is slow and the welding width is greater than the welding groove in the workpiece. The groove width during welding regulates the amount of deposited metal in order to achieve high quality welds, so in this case, the trainee needed to new electrode to complete the workpiece welding, a new welding electrode in practical field means additional cost required, so to develop the performance, the trainee can repeat the test.

It is useful to mention here, the current system able the trainees to get new virtual electrode by push the common of "**New Electrode**" in the 22" touch screen, in this case the welding electrode will be move forward by motor till reach the required electrode length, in this case, the trainee push "**Finish electrode replacement**" and complete the welding test (see figure 6.19).

In order to minimize the number of figures, both the working angle and travel angle of trainee no.2 are shown in figure 6.20:

Figure 6.20 Variation of working angle and travel with time for 1G Flat Groove for trainee no.2

Figure 6.20 shows in the 1G flat groove, the trainee no.2 performance is accepted since both travel angle and working angle are accepted. In the working angle, the trainee save his position within 0° - 3° to the recommended value of 45° , while in travel angle the same behavior occurs and the trainee worked near the recommended value of 20° - 30° .

Regarding to the welding arc length, the resulted data will be discussed together with 2G horizontal groove.

The gradually increasing in the performance is leading to say the virtual welding process in the correct direction in this course.

6.2.3.2 Welding Parameters Effects of 2G Horizontal Groove

The resulted virtual welding view in the 2G horizontal groove is shown in the figure 6.21.

Figure 6.21 Virtual welding view of 2G Horizontal Groove

The overall view of the virtual welding process on the 2G horizontal groove represented by figure 6.21 shows the process is quite good where welding width covered all grooved region without any extra region over or down the groove.

Regarding to the travelling speed, although the long time interval which reached to 146 s but the travel speed still accepted, where the extra time required to fill the groove with molten metal.

For the working travel angles, there is a limitation to draw both angles in the same figure because the recommended work angle in such type of position (2G horizontal groove) is 0° where the electrode perpendicular to the horizontal workpiece.

Figure 6.22 shows the working angle variation during the welding process.

Figure 6.22 Working angle variation of trainee no.2 on 2G Horizontal Groove

From figure 6.22, there are several results can be drawn such as:

- During the entire virtual welding process time interval, the working angle variation is accepted.
- The trainee stills in the same working angle for long time that means the stability of trainee hand is developed.
- There is a good response from the trainee to the system alarm when the trainee is far from the recommended value, which is noticed in beginning of the welding process and in about 30 s and in about 110s.

Regarding to the travel angle, the situation is not different and all the notices, which mentioned in working angle can be noted in travel angle with limited changes. It is useful to mention that the recommended values of the travel angle stills between 20°-30°. Figure 6.23 shows the variation of the travel angle with respect to the time during the virtual welding with 2G horizontal position.

Figure 6.23 Travel angle variation of trainee no.2 on 2G Horizontal Groove

Regarding to the welding arc length effect, the selected time interval will be taken as 20-30s, the effect of both cases will be studied together. Figure 6.24 shows the variation of welding arc length for 1G flat groove and 2G horizontal groove for trainee no.2

Figure 6.24 Arc length variation on 1G Flat Groove and 2G Horizontal Groove with selected time interval

The values of welding arc length for student no.2 in both 1G flat groove and 2G horizontal groove arc accepted with the 3.2mm recommended values where the electrode of E6010/E6011-1/8"(3.2mm) is used.

The closed arc length values with recommended values means that the trainee performance is developed and the system became more familiar to the trainee that is the main objective of the study on virtual welding system.

6.2.4 Case 4: Tee Joint Horizontal Position (2F)

In the current case study and the next cases, the virtual welding process view will be discussed only since all trainees will not access to this stage without get approval on the primary three cases which mention in last sections.

In current case a plate material Mild Steel 10 gauge, so a single process with electrode of E6010/E6011-1/8"(3.2mm) will use to represent the virtual welding process.

The recommended working angle is 45° and the recommended travel angle between 20° to 30° while the recommended arc length is 3.2mm, which is the same of the selected electrode.

The virtual welding process for 2F horizontal tee can be selected from trainee no.2 as shown in figure 6.25.

Figure 6.25 Virtual welding process on 2F Horizontal Tee

The travel speed is very accepted and the main view accepted where the welding width covered all preferred area. Furthermore, the welding shape is smooth.

It is useful to mention as soon as the current virtual welding can able to develop the skills and performance of the trainees, it is also an excellent educational tool to assist the trainers. It provides several guides so that trainee mistakes and progress may be analyzed. Detailed analysis allows the trainer to view the cause of mistakes and to analyze how the trainee is progressing. The trainer may also set the various training stages and modify them at any moment, thereby adapting the training course to the individual learner's particular needs.

6.2.5 Case 5: Tee Joint Vertical Position (3F)

In this case a plate material Mild Steel 10 gauge with a single process electrode of E6010/E6011-1/8"(3.2mm) are used to represent the virtual welding process.

The recommended value for working angle is 0° perpendicular to vertical tee workpiece while the travel angle is still within 20° - 30° , also the recommended value still 3.2 mm.

The virtual welding process of the trainee no.1 is shown in figure 6.26.

Figure 6.26 Virtual welding process on 3F Vertical Tee

Figure 6.26 shows the welding travel speed on virtual welding is accepted till the last section in the bottom of the joint where the travel speed increase more than the last parts which lead to the welding view to became a weak , the trainee re-correct his speed and the welding improve in last seconds.

In this case, the trainer can able to demand from the trainee to improve his skill by several extra experiments.

6.2.6 Case 6: Tee Joint Overhead Position (4F)

In this case a plate of Mild Steel 10 gauge material, so a single process with electrode of E6010/E6011-1/8"(3.2mm) will be used to represent the virtual welding process.

In overhead welding the recommended working angle range is 40°-45° with respect to the joint that is faced the trainee while the recommended travel angle closed with about 15° [1, 56]. The recommended welding arc length is 3.2mm for welding electrode E6010/E6011.

The overall view of the virtual welding process for 4F overhead tee welding can be shown in figure 6.27 for trainee no.2

Figure 6.27 Virtual welding process on 4F Overhead Tee

Although the trainee begin with a good welding, the welding view in the last section is not quite good. The travel speed is accepted in all welding process.

Welding in the 4G or 4F position of overhead is the most difficult of the out-of-position welds. The major challenge in this type of welding is controlling the weld puddle. The procedures for performing overhead welds are very similar to the flat position, except that they are far more difficult. It is necessary to pay special attention to the weld puddle and travel speed. The trainee must be maintaining a short arc as well and find a position that is comfortable for him before starting to weld. For these reasons, the virtual welding is quite useful to teach the trainee the accepted positions and the accepted welding arc length.

Finally, the virtual welding is not a tool for welding training instead of real welding training but it is a supporting tool and it is able to help both the trainers and the trainee to finish the training courses with lowest cost and with lowest period of time.

Chapter Seven

Conclusions and Recommendations

CHAPTER SEVEN

Conclusions & Recommendations

7.1 Conclusions

The virtual welding training is a new learning channel in innovative learning methodology by image improvement of welder training education. The main concepts, which are concluded from the current project, are:

1. A virtual welding machine is designed and constructed to teach new welding trainees and to help the trainers to minimize the training cost, training time and welding health problems.
2. The whole cost of constructed system is minimized by using low cost sensors such as IMU, LVDT, Optical encoders, and ultrasound sensors.
3. All required equations are solved and a software is built with VB.net, the software is ready for using now and it is covered all welding positions and all required welding electrodes.
4. Trainees' performance is studied on six case studies where most of the welding positions are covered. The system gives good results to learn the required welding parameters; welding travel angle, welding working angle, welding travel speed and welding arc length.
5. The using image coordinate analysis with LVDT sensor and touch screen tools give an accepted values to simulate arc welding which lead to minimize the whole system cost.
6. The Vectornav VN-100 which is used as inertial measurement unit (IMU) give good results to represent the welding working angle and the welding travel angle. The good response of the VN-100 lead to easy to find any welding angle at any time.
7. The construction gearbox that is reduced the speed of the motor gives an accepted speed closed with real consumption of welding electrode.
8. The touch screen prototype in BasVW 1.1, which uses to simulate the welding coupons consider as a good tool in virtual welding process.

7.2 Recommendations

There are several procedure can be added to the current project to become more active and became covered multi types of welding, the recommended items can be listed here:

1. develop the current model for Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW), with several modifications the current model can be covered GMAW such built new welding simulated gun do not including motor, steel rod, gear box and optical encoder. Also, replace the recommended date of SMAW with GMAW for welding angles, arc length and travel speed.
2. Develop the Helmet model by using wireless receiver and receptor which lead to minimize the system cables and give a user a more degree of freedom to overcome the helmet cables limitations.
3. Develop the BasVW 1.1 by using welding coupons and image-processing technique instead of using touch screen as welding environment. The recommended technique depending upon study the welding parameters (welding angles, arc length and travel speed) according take instantaneous pictures of virtual welding process and make an image processing as online with welding process.
4. Using 3D graphic tools such as OpenGL may be increase the accuracy of the display of the virtual welding process that will lead in general to become closed with real welding process.
5. Using high-resolution screen and high quality AV camera instead of the commercial units in Helmet design.
6. Minimize the whole machine size to be mobile unit that is easy to use and carry.

References

REFERENCES

- [1] Woodhead, K. W., Welding Processes Handbook Publishing Ltd, 2003.
- [2] Porter, N., C., Cote, Gifford, Lam, J., Virtual Reality Welder Training, Session 5: Joining Technologies for Naval Applications, Proceedings of 1st Cambridge Workshop on Universal Access and Assistive Technology, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK, 2002.
- [3] A Study of an Automatic Welding System, C. Y. Lee, PhD thesis, National Central University, Taiwan, Republic of China, July 2007.
- [4] American Welding Society, AWS A3.0, "Standard Welding Terms and Definitions," 12th Edition, 2001.
- [5] Bohnart, E., Welding: Principles & Practices, McGraw Hill, 4th edition, 2012.
- [6] Jeffus, L., Welding Skills, Processes and Practices for Entry-Level Welders: Book 1, Cengage Learning, Inc., 1st Edition, 2010.
- [7] Qingwei, G., Weining, Y., Qicheng, L., Triangle Mesh Optimization for Improving Rendering Quality of 3D Virtual Environments in Virtual Reality II, Second International Conference, ICVR 2007 Held as part of HCI International 2007, Beijing, China, July 22-27, 2007.
- [8] Naoto, K., Kazuya, O., Takashi, T., Hiroyuki, Y., VR-Based Self Brain Surgery Game System by Deformable Volumetric Image Visualization in Virtual Reality II ,Second International Conference, ICVR 2007 Held as part of HCI International 2007, Beijing, China, July 22-27, 2007.
- [9] Fast, K., Gifford, T., and Yancey R., Virtual Training for Welding, Proceedings of the Third IEEE and ACM International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR 04), (pp. 298-299), 2004.
- [10] Freeze, W., S., Windows Game Programming with Visual Basic and DirectX, Que Publisher, 1 edition, 2001.
- [11] Jones, W., Beginning DirectX 9 (Game Development Series), Publisher: Cengage Learning PTR; 1 edition, April, 2004.

References

- [12] Richard Simon, Microsoft Windows 2000 API SuperBible, Publisher: Sams Pub, 2000.
- [13] Harvey B. S and Macy L. A, "Arc Welding Simulator Trainer", U.S. Patent, No. US 3867769, 1975.
- [14] Bruce A. B, " Device for Teaching and Evaluating a Person's Skill as a Welder", U.S. Patent, No. US 4124944, 1978.
- [15] Boris E. P, Vsevolod V. V, Valentin A. B, Alexandr I. P, Sergei N. D, Viktor A. S, Vladimir A. C, Vitaly I. V, Viktor M. G, and Vsevolod N. B, "Welder's Trainer", U.S. Patent, No. US 4680014, 1987.
- [16] Boris E. P, Vsevolod V. V, Valentin A. B, Alexandr I. P, Sergei N. D, Viktor A. S, Vladimir A. C, Vitaly I. V, Viktor M. G, and Vsevolod N. B, "Electric Arc Trainer For Welders", U.S. Patent, No. US4716273, 1987.
- [17] Donald H., Richard F., David F., and Bruce, B., "Device for Training Welders", U.S. Patent, No. US4931018, 1990.
- [18] Geert K., "A Device for Assisting in Manual Welding Using a Plurality of Mark Light Projecting Units" European Patent Office, No. EP2036648 (A1), 2009.
- [19] Boulware, P., and Forquer, B., "Welder Training Technology: Accelerated Practice to Production", 2nd Internal Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany, 26 - 27 September, 2012.
- [20] Cook G. E., Strauss A. M., Lammlein D. H., and Fleming P. A., "Arc Sensors in Weld Monitoring", "Real-Time Weld Process Monitoring". Woodhead Publishing Limited, Cambridge England, pp. 15-43, 2008.
- [21] Saeed G. M., "Optical Sensors in Welding", "Real-Time Weld Process Monitoring". Woodhead Publishing Limited, Cambridge England, pp. 45-72, 2008.
- [22] Yang H., Wikle H. C., Nagarajan S., and Johnson M., "Infrared Sensors in Welding". "Real-Time Weld Process Monitoring". Woodhead Publishing Limited, Cambridge England, pp. 74-99, 2008.

References

- [23] Shao J. and Yan Y., "Ultrasonic Sensors in Welding". "Real-Time Weld Process Monitoring". Woodhead Publishing Limited, Cambridge England, pp. 104-124, 2008.
- [24] Ancona A. and Sibillano T., "Monitoring Laser Welding". "Real-Time Weld Process Monitoring". Woodhead Publishing Limited, Cambridge England, pp. 260-284, 2008.
- [25] Waterworth, J. A., "Virtual Reality in Medicine: a Survey of the State of the Art", in "Medicine Meets Virtual Reality 13: The Magical Next Becomes the Medical Now", IOS Press, 1999.
- [26] Michel D. and Dominique S., "Simulation and Teaching by Apprenticeship of A Manual Task Such as Arc Welding", France Patent FR2827066, 2003.
- [27] Aiteanu, D., Hillers, B., Graser, A., "A Step Forward in Manual Welding: Demonstration of Augmented Reality Helmet", Proceedings of the Second IEEE and ACM International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality ISMAR 2003, Tokyo, October 2003.
- [28] Wilhelm B., Kai S., "Remote Control of Real and Virtual Welding Robots for Learning", in "Cost Oriented Automation 2004". A Proceedings Volume from the 7th IFAC Symposium, Gatineau, Canada, ELSEVIER Publication, pp. 215-219, 6-9 June 2004.
- [29] Mavrikiosa, D., Karabatsoua, V., Fragosa, D., and Chryssolourisa, G., "A Prototype Virtual Reality-Based Demonstrator for Immersive and Interactive Simulation of Welding Processes", International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing Volume 19, Issue 3, 2006.
- [30] Park, M., Schmidt, L., Schlick, C., and Luczak, H., "Design and Evaluation of an Augmented Reality Welding Helmet", Human Factors and Ergonomics in Manufacturing & Service Industries, Volume 17, Issue 4, pages 317–330, July/August 2007.
- [31] Dongsik, J., Yongwan, K., Ungeon, Y., Lee, A., and Choi, J., S., "Visualization of Virtual Weld Beads" VRST '09 Proceedings of the 16th ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology, ACM New York, 2009.

References

[32] Teeravarunyou S. and Poopatb B., "Computer Based Welding Training System" , International Journal of Industrial Engineering, 16(2), 116-125, 2009.

[33] Zboray D.A., Bennett M. A., Wallace M. W., Hennessey J., Lenker, Z. S., Lundell A. B., Dana P., Preisz E. A., Briggs, L., Droller R. B., And Briggs, E. C., " Virtual Reality Pipe Welding Simulator", U.S. Patent, No. US 062406 A1, 2010.

[34] Peters C., Justice E. L., Gandee C., Zboray D. A., Bennett M. A., Wallace M. W., Manchester J. H. , Zachary Steven Lundell A. P. , Droller R. B. , and Briggs E. C., "Welding Simulator Console", U.S. Patent, No. US D631,074 S, 2011.

[35] Heston, T., Virtually welding Training in a virtual environment gives welding students a leg up, The FABRICATOR® | An FMA Publication, March 2008.

[36] Choquet, C. "Arc+: Today's Virtual Reality Solution for Welders", In International Conference of Safety and Reliability of Welded components in Energy and Processing Industry on the occasion of the 61th IIW Annual Assembly Conference, 2008.

[37] Ahrens, C., and Keitel, S., "Modern Developments in Education and Training in Welding and in Testing of Materials", 1st Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany 08 - 09 September, 2010.

[38] Bornert A., "Reality and Simulation and Its Useful Combination", 1st Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany, 08 - 09 September, 2010.

[39] Benus, F., and Da Dalto, L., "The use and benefits of Virtual Reality tools for the welding training", 1st Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany, 08 - 09 September, 2010.

[40] Kreindl, J., "Virtual Welding – a Modern, Innovative Simulation System for Education in Welding", 1st Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany, 08 - 09 September, 2010.

References

- [41] Rautert, H., "WELDING TRAINER, New Opportunities of Modular Training", 1st Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany, 08 - 09 September, 2010.
- [42] Hillers, B., Alegre V., M., and Gräser , A., "Augmented Reality- The Third Way for New Technologies in Welding Education", 1st Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany, 08 - 09 September, 2010.
- [43] Richard T. Stone, Kristopher P. Watts, Peihan Zhong , "Physical and Cognitive Effects of Virtual Reality Integrated Training", in " Human Factors: The Journal of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society" vol. 53 no. 5 558-572, October 2011.
- [44] Yunus, F., A., Hashim, J., Masran, S., H., Baser, B., "Virtual Reality Simulator Developed Welding Technology Skills", Proceedings of The IETEC'11 Conference, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 2011
- [45] Dongsik, J., Kim, Y., Yang, U, Kim, K.,H., Shin, S., ,"Real-time Graphical Presentation from Empirical Data for Virtual Welding Tasks", 5th ACM SIGGRAPH Conference and Exhibition on Computer Graphics and Interactive Techniques in Asia, Singapore , December 2012.
- [46] Bednarzik, M., Kaftan H., J., and Schulz, S., "Analyses of the Cost Efficiency while Using GSI SLV Welding Trainer in Training of Welders", 2nd Internal Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany, 26 - 27 September, 2012.
- [47] Gray, A., and Richter, A., "Arc :+Trends in Welding Education and the Advantages and Economics of Simulation in Welder Training", 2nd Internal Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany, 26 - 27 September, 2012.
- [48] Peters, C., and Wallace, M., "Building a Better Simulation: Expanding the Quality and Value of Simulation for the Welding Industry", 2nd Internal Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany, 26 - 27 September, 2012.

References

- [49] Engh, E., "Utilizing Virtual Welding Technology and Activity Based Training in order to transfer Skills, Knowledge and Competence in a Life-Long Learning Context", 2nd Internal Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany, 26 - 27 September, 2012.
- [50] Havenith, H., Koppel, U., and Klein, H., M., "VWTS The New Educational Course for Welders", 2nd Internal Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany, 26 - 27 September, 2012.
- [51] Middeldorf, K., "Guidelines for the Use of VWTS - Virtual Welding Training Systems", 2nd Internal Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", Duisburg, Germany, 26 - 27 September, 2012.
- [52] Rein, R., and Biallas, B., "Studying Welding Ergonomics in Novice and Expert Welders Using Virtual Welding", 2nd Internal Technical Conference WELDING TRAINER, "The Future of Education", 2010.
- [53] Mark W. S. , Hutchinson, S. and Vidyasagar, M., "Robot Dynamics and Control ", second edition, E. Books, 2004.
- [54] Shoemake, K., Animating Rotation with Quaternion Curves Proc. Computer Graphics (Proceedings of SIGGRAPH 85), 19(3):245–254, July 1985.
- [55] Mukundan, R., Advanced Methods in Computer Graphics: With examples in OpenGL, DOI 10.1007/978-1-4471-2340-8 5, © Springer-Verlag London Limited, 2012.
- [56] Kalman, R. E., A new approach to linear filtering and prediction problems, in Transaction of the ASME Journal of Basic Engineering, 82 (Series D): 35-45,1960.
- [57] Maybeck, P. S., Stochastic Models, Estimation, and Control, Volume1, Academic Press, 1979.
- [58] McMillan, G. and Considine, M., Process Industrial Instruments & Control Handbook, fifth edition, McGraw-Hill, 1999.

References

[59] Sacks, R., and Bohnart, E., Welding Principles and Practices, 3rd Edition, McGraw Hill, 2005.

[60] Jiluan, P., Arc welding control, Woodhead Publishing Limited, 1st edition, 2003.

[61] Siskind, S., Electrical Control Systems in Industry, McGraw-Hill, Inc., 1963.

[62] Welding Handbook, Lincoln Company, 2010.

Appendices

Appendix A Certifications

REPUBLIC OF IRAQ
Ministry of Industry and Minerals
Ibn Majid State CO.

جمهورية العراق
وزارة الصناعة والمعادن
شركة ابن ماجد العامة

العدد/ ف/ 430
التاريخ/ 30 /10/ 2013

الس/ جامعة البصرة /كلية الهندسة م /تقيم جهاز تدريب اللحامين

بعد معاينة الجهاز المقدم من قبل السيد رحيم خزل مصول طالب الدكتوراه في كلية الهندسة جامعة البصرة واجراء عدة اختبارات عليه ، كانت النتائج كالتالي.

1. الجهاز يوفر الكثير من الامكانيات مثل:

أ- اختبار نوع سلك اللحام.

ب- اختبار وضعية اللحام.

ت- اختبار شكل قطعة اللحام.

ث- قياس زوايا اللحام والتي تحسب بشكل تقريبي في الوضع العملي.

ج- يقوم الجهاز بتحديد سرعة اللحام بدون الحاجة الى وسائل خارجية مثل ساعة التوقيت.

2. الجهاز يعطي المعلومات الاساسية عن اللحام وهذا سيختصر كثيرا من وقت المحاضرات النظرية عند اجراء كورسات التدريب.

3. الجهاز يوفر الكثير من كلفة التدريب فلا يحتاج الى تهيئة نماذج حقيقية ومستلزمات العمل الأخرى.

4. بالامكان تطوير امكانيات الجهاز ليشمل انواع اخرى من اللحام.

واستنادا لما ورد اعلاه ومن خلال خبرتنا في مجال اللحام فيعتبر هذا الجهاز تجربة رائدة والأولى في العراق.

رئيس المهندسين
هيثم عبد الكريم عوده
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2013/10/ 30

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Confirmation

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"The Future of Education"

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DVS

Appendix B Vectornav VN-100

Quaternion used by VectorNav

While different organizations use different ordering of the terms, all quaternions fundamentally represent the same thing. Here are the equations for each of the terms used in our quaternion.

$$q_0 = e_x \sin\left(\frac{\vartheta}{2}\right)$$

$$q_1 = e_y \sin\left(\frac{\vartheta}{2}\right)$$

$$q_2 = e_z \sin\left(\frac{\vartheta}{2}\right)$$

$$q_3 = \cos\left(\frac{\vartheta}{2}\right)$$

Appendix C LabJack HV U3

B. Enclosure & PCB Drawings

The square holes shown below are for a DIN rail mounting adapter: Tyco part #TKAD.

Units are inches.

Appendix D LVDT

Soway

LVDT Displacement sensor

Mechanical Specifications

Specifications	SDVBS series of spring-loaded		
Measuring range (mm)	2.5	5	10
Body A (mm)	88	98	118
Iron core B (mm)	8	11	18

Wiring

Caution

When "yellow" on the same phase as "black", connected "blue" and "green" can output signal between "red" and "black", output and input is same phase, when the iron core is shift toward the cable.

SMS-100A2 Sizes

SMS-100A1 Sizes

Appendix E

LV-MaxSonar-EZ4™

MB1040

LV-MaxSonar®-EZ4™ High Performance Sonar Range Finder

With 2.5V - 5.5V power, the LV-MaxSonar®-EZ4™ provides very short to long-range detection and ranging, in an incredibly small package. The LV-MaxSonar®-EZ4™ detects objects from 0-inches to 254-inches (6.45-meters) and provides sonar range information from 6-inches out to 254-inches with 1-inch resolution. Objects from 0-inches to 6-inches range as 6-inches. The interface output formats included are pulse width output, analog voltage output, and serial digital output.

A	0.785"	19.9 mm	H	0.100"	2.54 mm
B	0.870"	22.1 mm	J	0.610"	15.5 mm
C	0.100"	2.54 mm	K	0.645"	16.4 mm
D	0.100"	2.54 mm	L	0.735"	18.7 mm
E	0.670"	17.0 mm	M	0.065"	1.7 mm
F	0.510"	12.6 mm	N	0.038" dia	1.0 mm dia
G	0.124" dia	3.1 mm dia	weight, 4.3 grams		

values are nominal

Features

- Continuously variable gain for beam control and side lobe suppression
- Object detection includes zero range objects
- 2.5V to 5.5V supply with 2mA typical current draw
- Readings can occur up to every 50mS, (20-Hz rate)
- Free run operation can continually measure and output range information
- Triggered operation provides the range reading as desired
- All interfaces are active simultaneously
- Serial, 0 to Vcc, 9600Baud, 81N
- Analog, (Vcc/512) / inch
- Pulse width, (147uS/inch)
- Learns ringdown pattern when commanded to start ranging
- Designed for protected indoor environments
- Sensor operates at 42KHz
- High output square wave sensor drive (double Vcc)

Benefits

- Very low cost sonar ranger
- Reliable and stable range data
- Sensor dead zone virtually gone
- Lowest power ranger
- Quality beam characteristics
- Mounting holes provided on the circuit board
- Very low power ranger, excellent for multiple sensor or battery based systems
- Can be triggered externally or internally
- Sensor reports the range reading directly, frees up user processor
- Fast measurement cycle
- User can choose any of the three sensor outputs

Beam Characteristics

Many applications require a narrower beam or lower sensitivity than the LV-MaxSonar®-EZ1™. MaxBotix® Inc., is offering, the EZ2™, EZ3™, & EZ4™ with progressively narrower beam angles allowing the sensor to match the application. Sample results for the LV-MaxSonar®-EZ4™ measured beam patterns are shown below on a 12-inch grid. The detection pattern is shown for: (A) 0.25-inch diameter dowel, note the narrow beam for close small objects, (B) 1-inch diameter dowel, note the long narrow detection pattern, (C) 3.25-inch diameter rod, note the long controlled detection pattern, (D) 11-inch wide board moved left to right with the board parallel to the front sensor face and the sensor stationary. This shows the sensor's range capability.

Note: The displayed beam width of (D) is a function of the specular nature of sonar and the shape of the board (i.e. flat mirror like) and should never be confused with actual sensor beam width.

beam characteristics are approximate

MaxBotix® Inc.

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PD10009e

الخلاصة

في هذه الدراسة تم تصميم وتصنيع نظام متكامل يخص عمليات اللحام الافتراضي لتعليم المتدربين الجدد عمليات اللحام. من الملاحظ في الحالة العملية ان هناك العديد من المتطلبات التي تحتاجها عمليات تدريب اللحامين. ان معادن اللحام واقطاب اللحام ومكائن اللحام بالاضافة الى معدات سحب ابخرة اللحام جميعها متطلبات لا بد من توفرها في كل عملية تدريب. ان الدراسة الحالية تقترح اقامة مختبر لحام افتراضي يمكن من خلاله محاكاة عملية التدريب الحقيقية دون الحاجة الى مثل هكذا متطلبات.

خلال العقدين الاخيرين تم تسجيل تسعة براءات اختراع حول العالم في موضوع اللحام الافتراضي وخلال الثلاث سنين الماضية استضافة المانيا المؤتمران الدوليان الاول والثاني لتقنيات اللحام الافتراضي.

تسمح الدراسة الحالية للمستخدم محاكاة وتجربة معظم الظروف الموجودة في اللحام، فهي تُعلم المهارات اللازمة للتنسيق بين اليد والعين في عمليات اللحام، فمن خلال النموذج المستخدم توفر الدراسة متابعة آنية للمتدرب لدراسة تأثير طول القوس وزوايا اللحام وسرعة الانتقال الصحيحة بالاضافة الى محاكاة استهلاك قطب اللحام وتسجيل كافة الاخطاء والذي يعني على نحو الاجمال تقليل تكاليف التدريب وتقليل الزمن اللازم للتدريب.

في المشروع الحالي فان تدريب اللحامين في لحام القوس الكهربائي المعدني المغطى (SMAW) يقترب من الواقع، ومن اجل حفظ معلومات التجارب ومعلومات المستخدمين الذين أجروا التجارب على جهاز محاكاة اللحام الافتراضي ، يقوم النظام بحفظ تلك النتائج على قاعدة بيانات حيث يمكن من خلالها اعداد التقارير الضرورية، بحيث تكون النتائج على شكل رسوم او على شكل نتائج تقييم.

تم استخدام متحسسات منخفضة الكلفة في تصميم وبناء نظام تدريب اللحام الافتراضي الحالي، حيث تم استخدام متحسسات تستخدم الامواج فوق الصوتية والاشعة تحت الحمراء ومتحسسات ضوئية لتسجيل الازاحة الدورانية بالاضافة الى متحسسات الازاحة الخطية (LVDT) ومتحسسات تعتمد مبدأ القصور الذاتي (IMU). ان نظام اللحام الافتراضي الحالي مكون وحدة مشاهدة افتراضية مكونة من (خوذة وشاشة تعمل باللمس قياس 22 بوصة) وادوات اللحام الافتراضي (قبضة لحام ونماذج لحام) بالاضافة الى جهاز حاسوب وعدة انواع من المحولات. تتكون المحولات من محول تناظري الى رقمي (ADC) مع محول رسومات الفيديو (VGA) بالإضافة إلى العديد من الموصلات الكهربائية لتغيير مصادر امدادات الطاقة تبعاً للبرنامج.

الخوذة المستخدمة طورت لكي تكون اكثر موائمة لكلا عمليات اللحام الافتراضي والحقيقي، وعليه فان الشكل الرئيسي للخوذة بقي على ما هو عليه في الخوذة الحقيقية بينما الشاشة

المستقطبة ابدلت بشاشة قياس 8 بوصة بالاضافة الى كاميرا ، عندما تحصل عملية اللحام الافتراضي فان الشاشة الموجودة في الخوذة سوف تعرض عملية اللحام اعتماد على المعلومات الواردة من جهاز الحاسوب بينما عند توقف عملية اللحام فان الشاشة الموجودة في الخوذة سوف تعرض ما يحيط بالمتدرب من خلال الكامرا المزودة بها الخوذة.

تم دراسة ست حالات للحام الافتراضي ، هذه الحالات شملت جميع اوضاع اللحام في لحام القوس الكهربائي المعدني المغطى. تم دراسة الصفيحة المستوية والصفيحة ذات الشق والمقاطع القائمة في اللحام الافقي والعمودي ولحام فوق الرأس. كذلك تم دراسة تأثير طول القوس وسرعة اللحام بالاضافة الى زوايا اللحام. ان النتائج كانت مقبولة جدا وجعلت المتدربين اكثر قابلية للتعامل مع اللحام الحقيقي.

تصميم وبناء نظام تدريب اللحام الافتراضي في

لحام القوس الكهربائي المعدني المغطى

(SMAW)

رسالة مقدمة الى

كلية الهندسة – جامعة البصرة

كجزء من متطلبات نيل درجة

دكتوراه فلسفة في الهندسة الميكانيكية

(ميكانيك تطبيقي)

تقدم بها

رحيم خزعل مصول

ماجستير علوم في الهندسة الميكانيكية

2013